

Expert Report

Fairness and Intersectional Non-Discrimination in Human Recommendation (FINDHR) Project

BEYOND THE ALGORITHM

Expanding the understanding of fairness and non-discrimination in algorithmic hiring

The case for Latin American migrants seeking for employment opportunities in Spain

By César Rosales, Nataly Buslón, Fabio Curi, Raquel Jorge

November 2023

Acknowledgements

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the numerous individuals and organizations whose unwavering support and contributions have made this research possible. This report, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program through the FINDHR (Fairness and Intersectional Non-Discrimination in Human Recommendation) project, exemplifies the collaborative spirit and dedication of the following:

The FINDHR Team: We owe a profound debt of gratitude to the dedicated and inspiring FINDHR team. Their commitment, time, support and invaluable insights have been instrumental in guiding and shaping the research. We express our appreciation to the following partners: Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF), WIDE+, PRAKSIS, as well as to the rest of the esteemed consortium partners.

Civil Society, Businesses and Industry Associations: We are indebted to the NGOs that have supported us in our pursuit of a more inclusive algorithmic hiring and rights landscape. Our sincere thanks go to Calala, Red Latinas, Alianza por la Solidaridad, La Fede.cat, Algorithights, Adigital, Intrare, CIVICAI, La Verneda and Shakers for their collaboration and shared vision.

Research Participants: We extend our gratitude to the participants in the focus groups whose valuable perspectives enriched our understanding of the subject matter. We are also thankful for the numerous anonymous participants in our surveys, whose contributions played a crucial role in our research. This project would not have been possible without the collaborative efforts, knowledge sharing, and dedication of each of these individuals and organizations. We deeply appreciate their support and involvement in this endeavor.

How to cite this report. Example: César Rosales, Nataly Buslón, Fabio Curi and Raquel Jorge (2023). Beyond the Algorithm: Expanding the understanding of fairness and non-discrimination in algorithmic hiring - The case for Latin American migrants seeking for employment opportunities in Spain. *FINDHR Expert Reports*.

More on FINDHR: <https://findhr.eu/> and <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070212>

This report was commissioned by project **Fairness and Intersectional Non-Discrimination in Human Recommendation (FINDHR)**, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101070212.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements.....	1
Table of Contents.....	2
List of Figures and Tables.....	3
Executive Summary.....	5
Introduction: Overview of the use of machine learning algorithms in the hiring process.....	6
Section 1: Theoretical Framework - Algorithmic Discrimination in Hiring.....	9
1.1 The Sociotechnical Aspect of Technology: Assessing the steering of technology in the field of hiring.....	9
1.2 Critical Theory: The relevance of intersectionality and overlapping disadvantages for algorithmic discrimination in hiring.....	12
1.3 On anti-discrimination law in the European Union and algorithmic discrimination.....	14
1.4 Conclusion.....	16
Section 2: Methodology.....	17
2.1 Mixed Methods, Communicative Methodology (CM) and Design Thinking (DT).....	17
2.1.1 Research questions.....	19
2.1.2 Field work.....	20
2.1.2.1 Target groups (methodology).....	21
2.1.2.2 Outreach strategy (methodology).....	21
2.1.2.3 Platform analysis (methodology).....	22
2.1.2.4 Perceptions of migrants (methodology).....	22
Section 3: Platform analysis and technology assessment.....	23
3.1. Uses of AI technology in the hiring process.....	24
3.2. Main challenges to develop trustworthy solutions.....	26
3.3. Current efforts to develop trustworthy technology.....	28
Section 4: Perceptions of affected groups.....	31
4.1. Perceptions of online platforms.....	31
4.2. Offline barriers: Main barriers.....	35
4.3. Online barriers.....	37
4.4. Challenges in job search participation.....	40
4.5. A real life example: A migrant's quest for employment using digital technologies.....	42
Section 5: Results and Discussion.....	45
5.1 Research question 1: At what stages of the hiring process are algorithmic fairness and non-discrimination perceived to be at odds by migrants from Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain?.....	45
5.2 Research question 2: How do intersecting characteristics of origin, gender, race, education, and socioeconomic standing, interact and create unique forms of algorithmic interaction?.....	46
5.3 Research question 3: How innovative strategies, visions and narratives could be harnessed to promote the development of robust, inclusive and trustworthy online platforms for hiring?.....	48

Section 6: Recommendations	52
6.1 Policy Recommendations.....	52
6.2 Target groups.....	54
6.2.1 Developers.....	54
6.2.2 Companies doing recruitment.....	56
6.2.3 Policymakers.....	57
6.2.4 Social communities.....	58
References	60
Annex	65
A1. Survey (Link to full results, questions and options).....	65
A2. Focus Groups.....	66
A2.1 Focus group with companies (Online, October 25th, 2023).....	66
A2.2 Focus groups with migrants (Barcelona and Bilbao, October 7th, 2023).....	69
A3. Interviews.....	72
A4. Outreach Materials.....	73
A4.1 LinkedIn/Facebook.....	73
A4.2 Twitter.....	74

List of Figures and Tables

Table 1. <i>Relationship between theoretical framework and methodology</i>	18
Figure 1. <i>Timeline of the project</i>	19
Table 2. <i>Main types of digital technologies employed in the hiring process as seen through the lens of the consulted population, which mostly interacts with job search platforms</i>	24
Table 3. <i>List of challenges faced by machine learning systems in hiring to avoid bias and discrimination</i>	27
Table 4. <i>Efforts undertaken by AI professionals to foster inclusion and non-discrimination in their technologies deployed in the hiring process.</i>	29
Figure 2: <i>Question 10. Main ways to look for employment</i>	32
Figure 3: <i>Question 12. Overall satisfaction with tools. 3.10/5.00 average</i>	32
Figure 4: <i>Question 13. Effectiveness perceived to search for a job. 2.67/5.00 average</i>	33
Figure 5: <i>Question 14. Familiarity and ease of use of the platforms. 3.09/5.00 average</i>	33
Table 5. <i>Perceptions from surveyed migrants on ease and trustworthy to use online platforms for search job</i>	34

Table 6. <i>List of offline challenges faced by migrant women to search for employment opportunities</i>	36
Figure 6: <i>Question 29. Not enough support resources to find employment</i>	37
Table 7. <i>List of online challenges faced by migrant women to search for employment opportunities</i>	39
Figure 7: <i>Question 25. Perceptions over discriminatory practice</i>	41
Figure 8: <i>Question 22. Platforms designed to prevent bias or discrimination</i>	41
Table 8. <i>List of main problems suffered by migrant women</i>	41
Case 1: <i>Woman working in the care sector</i>	43
Case 2: <i>Woman working at the intersection of technology and public policy</i>	44
Figure 9: <i>Question 17. Main Barriers</i>	48

Executive Summary

This report addresses algorithmic bias in hiring practices, driven by the increased use of online hiring platforms. While these technologies and tools promise to optimize recruitment processes and reduce human bias, they also have the potential of encoding and potentially reinforcing harmful biases and widen inequality gaps, in particular against certain groups under conditions of vulnerability or exclusion. The research investigates the challenges faced by groups in situations of vulnerability and marginalization, particularly migrants of Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain, throughout the hiring process. Additionally, it offers an assessment on whether online platforms and recruiters incorporate explicit ethical approaches into their product and service designs to prevent discriminatory practices.

The report incorporates a theoretical framework drawing from Social Theory and the Internet and Critical Theory to analyze the sociotechnical systemic dynamics behind algorithmic bias in hiring. The framework recognizes that matters related to fairness and non-discrimination are not isolated phenomena, but are deeply embedded within the social dynamics and development of technology. Additionally, the report focuses on intersectional discrimination faced by migrants from Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain, considering their unique identities, background and experiences based on their origin, age, gender, education, and socioeconomic standing. The concept of power and technology, based on Directed Technical Change, is also incorporated in the research to examine how dominant ideas, visions, and narratives within AI-based hiring technologies impact the development of inclusive and trustworthy platforms.

Based on field work, the report explores offline and online barriers to equal opportunities for Latin American migrants seeking employment opportunities in Spain. The research finds that most of the challenges the consulted population face take place in offline settings, i.e. before they interact with the internet and web applications. In this phase, the challenges take the form of structural impediments that prevent them from carrying out their professional activities related to their professional and academic background. Derived from this, most of the participants in the field work limit their use of digital technologies to social media platforms, job search engines and websites to look for employment, and do not even have the opportunity to engage with more sophisticated Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS) that might use machine learning algorithms to conduct rankings, interview analysis or job performance prediction. This lack of participation by this segment of the population was acknowledged by developers and recruiters as problematic from the point of view of collecting quality data as input for their systems to perform better with these communities.

Lastly, the report offers concrete recommendations for academic, civil society sector, policy, and industry stakeholders, along with the general public. These recommendations aim to address the identified challenges and promote fair, inclusive, and non-discriminatory hiring practices.

Introduction: Overview of the use of machine learning algorithms in the hiring process

Digital technology has rapidly transformed various aspects of society, and one area where its impact has been particularly pronounced is in the employment sector, in particular job and talent search. Over the past years, there has been a notable increase in the use of digital technologies to assist recruiters throughout the hiring process. In fact, according to a research published in 2020 by the asset management firm Mercer, over 7,300 human resources managers reported an increasing use of predictive analytics or similar systems, with adoption rates surging from approximately 10% in 2016 to around 39% in 2020 (Mercer, 2022). Automation systems have been increasingly utilized to expedite hiring processes, from job postings to resume scanning, interview analysis and job performance prediction. Current job hunt practices usually start in websites or online platforms like LinkedIn, Indeed, Infojobs, Careerbuilder, Glassdoor and even social media like Facebook or WhatsApp (Flynn, 2023). According to the offshore recruitment firm the Principle Group, the use of these websites is massive, as more than 830 million professionals are on LinkedIn, over 225 million resumes are on Indeed, and CareerBuilder registered over 80 million job applications with over 150 million candidate profiles and 3 million job posted each month (Principle Group, 2023). The aforementioned dynamic represents a major market opportunity for many firms willing to devote resources for the development of technologies to assist this process. In fact, a study by the research firm Technavio in 2022 projected the market share of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in the recruitment industry to rise to US\$223 million between 2021 and 2026. According to Technavio, the growing trend is primarily attributed to these technologies' ability to optimize the recruitment process through automated reviews, enhanced candidate relationship management, and the potential reduction of human bias (Technavio, 2022).

Despite the enthusiasm and the extensive incorporation of technology to enhance the hiring process, candidates encounter significant obstacles when attempting to identify suitable positions for application. The job search process often requires candidates to complete numerous time-consuming applications through various systems, leading to generic rejections. Research conducted by Zippia in 2023, based on data from 2021, revealed that 75% of online applications are rejected by applicant tracking systems (ATS) due to formatting issues. Furthermore, approximately 40% of surveyed candidates reported receiving no response from employers after applying for a position. Crafting a compelling resume (21%), gaining visibility (21%), and obtaining detailed feedback from employers (18%) remain substantial challenges that must be addressed to enhance the overall job search experience (Zippia, 2023). In this respect, Mitra Ebadollahi, senior project director for economic justice at Upturn, considers this dynamic disempowering to candidates (Davis, 2023).

The integration of machine learning into our daily lives, notably accelerated by the fast-paced adoption of digital technologies as a result of the impact of the COVID-19 global

pandemic, has spurred a shift in how both, companies and individuals, seek and share employment opportunities, as described by Liscomb (Liscomb 2022). This shift is at the core of what is commonly known as the "creator economy" or "social commerce," revolving around the creation, distribution, and sharing of digital content in today's digital landscape. Central to this transformation is the widespread use of social media platforms to advertise job openings, a practice embraced by recruiters, small businesses, and individuals alike (GRIN, n.d.). Strikingly, 79% of job seekers now incorporate social media into their job search processes, while over 90% of recruiters utilize platforms such as LinkedIn to identify potential candidates (Zippia, 2023). This new socio-economic dynamic, intertwining social media with job seeking and advertising, overlaps with the growing interest of recruiters in employing algorithms to enhance their hiring processes, resulting in a complex and multifaceted scenario. A deeper, more comprehensive, granular understanding of this evolving landscape is vital to ensure that the advantages of these technological advancements are equitably distributed across society for the benefit of the majority.

Perhaps the most important concern about the implementation of AI/ML-based technologies in the hiring process is its potential of encoding structural harmful biases and of increasing inequality gaps through the use of techniques to predict job performance, rank candidates and many other functionalities (Ghosh, Dutt, and Wilson 2021; Geyik, Ambler, and Kenthapadi 2019; Celis, Straszak, and Vishnoi 2017; Kleinberg, Mullainathan, and Raghavan 2016), as it has been documented by extensive academic research that has conducted algorithmic testing for discrimination showing that indeed most systems incur in discrimination against certain populations, and the challenge systems face with dealing with intersectionality (Köchling and Wehner 2023; Kassir et al. 2022; Peral and Geldenhuys 2020; Raghavan, Purohit, and Gollupadi 2019; Raghavan et al. 2020; Cathy O'Neil 2016). Yet, despite the academic research and awareness, there is ample room for knowledge generation about the social dynamics of specific groups around the development of these technologies, in particular to inform developers, recruiters, users, and policy makers on how to prevent the widening inequality gaps and the discrimination against marginalized and underrepresented groups.

Recent work on discrimination conducted by Londa Schiebinger (Tannenbaum, Ellis, Eyssel, Zou and Shiebinger 2019), Timnit Gebru and Joy Boulanwini (MIT Media Lab 2022), to name a few, has shown the importance of taking into consideration an intersectional approach when assessing and developing AI-based tools to understand how multiple forms of discrimination overlap, and in this case, how digital technologies using data and machine learning algorithms affect different groups of people seeking for jobs through online means. Both algorithmic auditing against discrimination and intersectional perspectives could be enriched by more comprehensive understanding of the interactions between humans and automated systems. In this sense, a segmented understanding of the algorithmic discrimination in the different stages of the selection and recruitment process (from the advertisement of job positions throughout the ranking of candidates in the platforms, interviews, and job performance prediction, among others) remains crucial for further academic research, policy making and product development (Morondo, Eguliz Castañeira,

and Álvarez 2022).

These analyses bear significant relevance in the context of ongoing global and regional governance and regulatory developments, particularly within Europe. Notably, the enactment of the General Data Protection Regulation in 2018, alongside upcoming regulations such as the AI Act, the Digital Services Act, and the Digital Markets Act, as well as EU law directives aimed at preventing discrimination, all play a crucial role. Furthermore, considerations extend beyond the EU, including non-EU bodies and agreements such as the Steering Committee on Anti-Discrimination, Diversity and Inclusion (CDADI) and the Committee on AI's "Revised Zero Draft [Framework] Convention on Artificial Intelligence, Human Rights, Democracy, and the Rule of Law" under the Council of Europe. Simultaneously, various overseas initiatives and national endeavors add to the current regulatory landscape.

This expert report offers a holistic perspective by incorporating elements from Social Theory, the Internet, and Critical Theory into its theoretical framework (section 1) to analyze the sociotechnical systemic dynamics behind algorithmic bias in hiring practices. Instead of solely concentrating on the statistical analysis of discriminatory patterns in algorithms, the report acknowledges that bias and discrimination are deeply entrenched in the social dynamics and technological evolution. In the methodology section (section 2), the report details a mixed-methods approach aligned with the theoretical framework. This approach involves conducting fieldwork through surveys, focus groups, and one-on-one interviews with migrants, developers, and recruiters. Subsequently, the report delves into two distinct sections based on the findings from this fieldwork. Platform analysis (section 3) evaluates popular web platforms and social media utilized by migrants and explores the technology underpinning developers' and recruiters' efforts to create robust, trustworthy systems, along with the primary challenges encountered in mitigating discrimination. The next section (section 4) delves into migrants' interactions with these tools, their unique experiences in job searching and advertising, and their perceptions regarding the advantages and fairness of using such technologies to access employment opportunities, as well as their concerns about discrimination. Both sections critically examine online and offline barriers faced by this demographic, providing valuable insights for the subsequent recommendations section. The report briefly discusses the results (section 5) and engages in a discussion, ultimately delivering recommendations (section 6) for developers, recruiters, users, and policymakers.

In the context of the Fairness and Intersectional Non-Discrimination in Human Recommendation (FINDHR) project, the ultimate goal of this report is to provide deeper understanding about the implications of algorithmic usage in the hiring process for migrant women from Latin American countries in the Spanish labor market, explore whether this situation leads to algorithmic discrimination scenarios, and which main challenges are derived from this reality, in both offline and online settings, for migrant women to search for jobs. This project is also aimed at fostering the development of reliable and trustworthy technologies in the field of hiring, and serve as a set of policy recommendations to adapt, frame and update the policies developed by three main target groups: public sector, private

sector (both developers and companies using AI for recruitment), and civil society organizations.

Section 1: Theoretical Framework - Algorithmic Discrimination in Hiring

Within the exploration of fairness and algorithmic discrimination conducted by the FINDHR project in the context of hiring practices, this report is based on a theoretical framework that draws upon insights from Social Theory and the Internet (Schroeder 2018) as well as Critical Theory (Hill Collins 2019), emphasizing the sociotechnical dynamics that underlie algorithmic bias in hiring processes (Draude et al. 2020; Dolata, Feuerriegel, and Schwabe, 2021). The report adopts a socio-technical perspective, scrutinizing the dimensions of bias and discrimination in the selection and recruitment process. It also takes an intersectional approach to understand elements of positionality and situated knowledge in the configuration of potentially discriminatory outcomes of algorithmic systems. The aim of this report is to unveil how both offline and online dynamics jointly influence the employment prospects of migrants of Latin American origin in Spain. Rather than merely delving into existing quantitative research on algorithmic discrimination, the focus of the report lies in comprehending the practical relationships at play: the *perceptions* from targeted groups (both Latin American migrant women and AI developers), and the degree of *knowledge* about the object of research -usage and uptake of AI in hiring process- that this project focuses on.

1.1 The Sociotechnical Aspect of Technology: Assessing the steering of technology in the field of hiring

The recognition of the intricate relationship and mutual shaping that occurs between society and technology (Draude et al. 2020) is a critical starting point for the analysis of algorithmic discrimination in the field of hiring. This “socio-technical” approach as it is known underscores the fact that technological development is not purely a technical matter, but a set of complex social practices that takes place within a specific institutional and organizational context (Sartori and Theodorou 2022). In the case of the selection and recruitment process, this translates into the value that technological tools provide to candidates and recruiters, as a technology designed to achieve certain goals like identifying the adequate talent to fulfill certain job vacancies, the support for candidates to apply for meaningful professional opportunities, as well as to optimize the management of people from the recruiter side. Therefore, on the human side, the design process of such tools is shaped by the goals of the recruiting and developer companies, as well as the need of candidates to use reliable tools to identify job positions. On the technological side, involved parties adapt to the dynamics generated by the way in which tools have been designed to generate specific results. Technology and social actors thus build an entangled web of relationships that shape both the objectives and features of the systems used in the hiring

process, as well as the use and perceptions by people of the use of such technology. Makarius et al. have conducted research on how organizations consider cognitive, relational and structural complexities to integrate technology into their workflows. The research argues that the successful integration of technologies like AI into organizational workflows or sectors depends on the type and quality of the collaboration between such systems and the people involved. The result of this interaction is called “socio-technical capital,” referring to the competitive advantage generated through a positive relationship between the technology and the people of the organization or sector (Makarius et al., 2020, Sartori and Theodorou, 2022). In the case of the hiring process, the socio-technical capital would be the result of shared benefits among developers, recruiters and candidates in successfully improving the overall recruiting industry. This research aims at understanding to what extent parties involved *know* and *consider* there is an actual socio-technical capital being generated or if there are *perceptions* of an asymmetric distribution of benefits.

In this sense, the perceptions of the use of such technology allows for the creation of narratives and stories about the fears and hopes in the use of technology (Sartori and Theodorou, 2022). These narratives can range from a wide array of perspectives including reductionistic views and assumptions over the role of technology in social progress, either overly optimistic (techno-optimism) or pessimistic about its impact. The more fundamentalistic views on the development and impact of technology are known as “technological determinism,” which invokes the idea that technological development is mostly unaltered by social influences being an autonomous force by itself driven by scientific advances and innovation (Smith and Marx 1994, Antonsen and Lundestad 2019).

The counter narrative of technological determinism is known as “social construction” or “social determinism”, which claims that social factors are primarily responsible for technological developments and that the use of any given technology depends on how it is socially determined (Sharma, 2018). From technological determinism to social construction or determinism in their optimistic and pessimistic variants, there is a myriad of perspectives in-between that play a role in the adoption of technology. This is why the analysis of the use and perceptions of a particular technology in a given process or sector requires the inclusion of a diverse set of users, developers, business leaders, and citizens (Dolata, Feuerriegel, and Schwabe 2021, Sartori and Theodorou 2022). The methodology of this report is especially designed to consult three main audiences involved in the use of technology and algorithms in the hiring process, which are: users, developers and recruiters, to understand their expectations, experiences and perceptions of the usefulness of technology in the particular field of hiring. By incorporating all these views, this research aims at offering a clearer understanding of the socio-technical dynamics behind the use of algorithms in hiring, as well as a more balanced set of recommendations to help build robust and trustworthy technologies.

Another relevant aspect for this research that is related to the socio-technical characteristics of the use of technology is the concept of “non-neutrality”. This concept highlights the fact that technology is not neutral in itself with no interest or agenda, but rather its development

follows a careful process of design, intentional decision-making, selection of features and parameters of the system, to ultimately exercise certain power that might include or exclude certain groups of people in the distribution of benefits generated by such technology. The researcher Ellen Rose has developed a triadic model that rejects the assumption that technology is neutral by analyzing how “every technology predisposes a certain use; how it shapes habits of mind and social organization; and how it is the outcome of deliberate choices made by individuals and societies” (Rose 2012). This report draws on the notion of non-neutrality by incorporating into the methodology and research questions aspects related to the analysis of how those who build and use these technologies (both developers and recruiters that use AI in the hiring process) orient their decisions in the design and deployment of such technologies into the hiring process.

Adjacent to the concept of technological non-neutrality lies the concept of “directed technological change” coined by MIT economist Daron Acemoglu and further expanded in the book “Power and Progress” (2023) co-authored with Simon Johnson. The main argument of their book is that the benefits of technology are not shared automatically, therefore an institutional arrangement is critical for the spillover to take effect, called the “productivity bandwagon”. In neo-classical economic theory this concept refers to the idea that technological progress increases average wages, thus being a critical element for the well-being of society. However, according to Acemoglu and Johnson, this does not happen spontaneously but under a consistent institutional setting of democratic political institutions, education and with countervailing forces that push for the redistribution of benefits for companies, workers and people.

What is relevant about the concept of directed technical change for this report is the idea that technological deployment is possible through a combination of vision and social power, the motto that “technology is nothing without a vision” (Acemoglu and Johnson 2023). This vision could only be exercised once adequate and sufficient material and immaterial resources are set in place to steer technology in certain directions. Because this is a matter of power being used by people, most of the innovators that direct these developments tend to fall into what is called the “vision trap”. Under this concept the visionary is so successful achieving certain commercial goals that this person tends to ignore human suffering, deemed as collateral, making bias less evident to their eyes (Acemoglu and Johnson 2023).

This report aims at understanding what are the visions and blind spots of the private sector in the development of technologies for the selection and recruitment process, as well as current proactive practices to create and use trustworthy technology. Additionally, by examining the dominant ideas, visions and narratives behind technological developments and the use of machine learning algorithms in the employment sector, the project will be in a better position of issuing specific and actionable recommendations for a number of academic, civil society, policy and industry stakeholders, as well as the public in general.

Moreover, this research is particularly interested in assessing perceptions of the impact of the use of technology in the field of hiring from the perspective of “algorithmic fairness”, a

concept that refers to the ethical and equitable use of machine learning algorithms in automated decision-making processes. It refers to the idea that algorithms should not discriminate against individuals and specific groups of people or lead to biased outcomes. The concept aims at ensuring that all individuals are treated fairly without bias regardless of their demographic characteristics such as race, gender, origin and other protected attributes (Wang, Zhang, and Zhu, 2022). As mentioned before, this research will look at the socio-technical dynamics and perceptions about fairness and non-discrimination in the use of algorithms in hiring, but not conduct in-depth analysis of particular algorithms encoding structural harmful biases through the use of techniques to predict job performance, rank candidates and other functionalities like prior research already has (Ghosh, Dutt, and Wilson 2021; Geyik, Ambler, and Kenthapadi 2019; Celis, Straszak, and Vishnoi 2017; Kleinberg, Mullainathan, and Raghavan 2016). This report also acknowledges the research testing and documenting discriminatory outcomes from machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms in hiring, but takes a more qualitative and analytical approach in the study of interactions as described in the methodology section (Köchling and Wehner 2023; Kassir et al. 2022; Peral and Geldenhuys 2020; Raghavan, Purohit, and Gollupadi 2019; Raghavan et al. 2020).

As described by scientific research, the inability of computing systems to address context dependent information is one of the most pressing causes for concern in the field of “algorithmic fairness” (Draude et al. 2020), given the fact that it is a problem not only circumscribed to technical parameters. According to Sartori and Theodorou, perhaps the main challenge in the use of algorithms from a socio-technical perspective is the impact these systems might cause beyond their actual capabilities with a potential to widen existing inequalities through a “magnifying glass” effect. The opacity of these systems, commonly referred to as “black boxes” (Pasquale, 2015) given their high level of computing complexity, adds a layer of difficulty to respect human agency and control. Furthermore, it remains a challenge to prevent structural inequalities to become inputs and outputs of such automated systems. (Sartori and Theodorou 2022). In order to properly address such structural inequalities, scholars like Draude highlight the importance holistic approaches and work between and across many disciplines, including the “importance of gender and diversity studies to bring expertise on bias and structural inequalities, which provide a crucial source for the analysis of algorithmic systems” (Draude et al. 2020).

1.2 Critical Theory: The relevance of intersectionality and overlapping disadvantages for algorithmic discrimination in hiring

The second major theoretical framework for this report is Critical Theory, more specifically notions about intersectionality (Crenshaw 1989), positionality and situated knowledge (Simandan 2019) stemming from gender and race studies to understand the challenges that certain groups of people face when interacting with algorithms in their search for employment. In the field of computer science, recent work on algorithmic discrimination conducted by Londa Schiebinger (Stanford University, n.d.), Timnit Gebru and Joy Buolamwini (MIT Media Lab, 2022), to name a few, has shown the importance of taking into

consideration an intersectional approach when assessing and developing AI-based tools to understand how multiple forms of fairness and non-discrimination overlap, and in this case, how platforms affect different groups of people seeking for jobs through online search.

In 1989 professor Kimberlé Crenshaw coined the term “intersectionality” to describe how individual characteristics like race, gender, class, and others overlap with one another, or “intersect”, and might create an experience of disadvantage (Coaston, 2019). According to Crenshaw in her historic text “Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex”, given the fact that the intersectional experience is greater than the sum of racism and sexism, or the disadvantages experienced through each individual demographic characteristics, any analysis that aims at addressing particular manners of subordination must take an intersectional approach to adequately address the matter (Crenshaw, 1989). The same analytical approach could be applied to understand the challenges that groups like migrants in Spain face when engaging with technological deployments that are supposed to aid their job search and exercise their right to employment without being discriminated against. This is where positionality and situated knowledge (Simandan 2019) become relevant for this study, as elements that allow the recognition that individuals possess unique and multifaceted identities and experiences that might face specific forms of bias or discrimination. On the one hand, “positionality” refers to the idea that one is located to their various identities and their combination (gender, race, origin, class, ethnicity, etc.) (Queens n.d.), thus shaping a particular understanding of the world and its contexts. This position is crucial to identify the particular dynamics of algorithmic fairness/discrimination a group might experience. On the other hand, the thesis of “situated knowledge” is deeply intertwined with the concept of positionality, underscoring the fact that one’s knowledge is incomplete and situated given the particular information about the world that reaches a person through particular channels and experiences (Simandan 2019). Because this world view is unique to individuals and groups, according to David Takacs, faculty scholar at the University of California, “only by listening to others can I become aware of the conceptual shackles imposed by my own identity and experiences” (Takacs 2003), in other words, one’s particular cognitive experience can be enriched by the interaction and contrast of epistemologies with others.

In the case of algorithmic discrimination, the understanding of epistemologies is as important as the understanding of how “epistemic communities” may interact and exchange with each other to promote a further deepening on this issue. Epistemic communities of practice, as described by E. Adler and M. Faubert, refer to groups of individuals who share a common understanding and knowledge within a specific domain or field (Adler and Faubert 2022). These communities are characterized by their collective expertise, established through mutual engagement and collaboration. Members of epistemic communities of practice collaborate to create and refine knowledge within their specialized area, emphasizing the importance of shared learning, communication, and social interaction in the process of knowledge construction. In the particular case of this report, two major epistemic communities are identified: those of users, in particular migrants from Latin America and the Caribbean in Spain, and the businesses that develop and deploy algorithms in hiring.

When addressing a topic like algorithmic discrimination in hiring it is crucial to directly consult the various groups engaging with a specific technology to understand their perceptions of potential discriminatory outcomes of the systems, as well as the epistemological gaps among groups. This report is interested in analyzing the epistemological gaps between businesses (developers and recruiters), and people or supposed beneficiaries of the system like job candidates (migrants from Latin America in Spain), i.e. what are the conceptual gaps or blindspots that might cause a specific technology to discriminate against a specific group of people resulting from the lack of awareness of businesses of the particular experience of such group of peoples.

In the field of applied machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence, scholars like Anaelia Ovalle et al, Joy Buolamwini, Londa Schiebinger and many others have argued the importance of adopting intersectionality as an analytical framework to operationalize notions of fairness. Ovalle, based on the analysis of over 30 papers from the AI fairness literature, has found that most of the research tends to reduce intersectionality to optimize for fairness metrics over demographic subgroups, placing more attention to harmful bias against individuals than to disparate impact among subgroups of people. Additionally, her research finds there is a lack of recognition of the power dynamics behind the design of AI-based systems focusing only on the AI pipeline (Ovalle et al. 2023). In a similar vein, Draude et al find that systems of classification and categorization have historically been used to advance oppressive agendas, therefore it is crucial to understand how this cultural dynamics offload onto technical systems at the data and algorithm levels (Draude et al. 2020).

This report also places attention to the dynamics that migrants in Spain experience when searching for employment opportunities, both through online dynamics, usually interacting with internet-based applications with machine-learning or data-based technologies, and offline dynamics like the challenges migrants face prior and during their interaction with automated systems of recruiting or job advertising. From the socio-technical standpoint, this is critical to get a fuller understanding of the dynamics behind algorithmic discrimination.

1.3 On anti-discrimination law in the European Union and algorithmic discrimination

One of the most relevant concepts for this report is that of discrimination and its various manifestations through the use of algorithms in the hiring process. This subsection provides an overview of EU law on discrimination, what it covers, as well as other international trends and efforts tackling algorithmic discrimination, it then offers a brief discussion of the implications of the treatment of discrimination from a legal/regulatory standpoint.

In this sense, research conducted by Raphaële Xenidis and Linda Senden illuminates the major risks of discrimination posed by algorithms through biased code, i.e. the design and development of systems that use certain variables that disproportionately or unfairly benefit

one group of people over the other. This includes the biased selection of features or attributes that might be proxy for protected attributes, as well as the incorrect handling of data and the use of biased training data that might end up permeating historical discrimination and exclusion (Xenidis and Senden 2020). Taking into consideration these dynamics on algorithmic discrimination, it is worth reviewing the existing EU legislation on non-discrimination and beyond, in order to understand the trends and dynamics of the implementation of such regulation in the use of machine learning algorithms in the field of hiring, with a particular focus on migrants.

According to scholars like Xenidis, Senden and Aytekin, the four most relevant EU directives to address discrimination are the following: (i) The Racial Equality Directive (2000/43/EC, 2000 OJ L 180/22) that prohibits discrimination on the basis of racial or ethnic origin in various contexts; (ii) The Employment Equality Directive (2000/78/EC, 2000 OJ L 303/16) that prohibits discrimination on the grounds of religion or belief, disability, age, or sexual orientation in the employment context; (iii) The Recast Gender Equality Directive (2006/54/EC, 2006 OJ L 204/23) that prohibits discrimination on the basis of gender in the employment context; and (iv) The Gender Goods and Services Directive (2004/113/EC, 2004 OJ L 373/37) that prohibits discrimination on the basis of gender in the context of the supply of goods and services. Together, the EU directives protect people against discrimination on the following six protected characteristics: age, gender, religion or belief, racial or ethnic origin, sexual orientation, disability (Xenidis and Senden 2020, Aytekin 2023). This report aims at understanding potential discriminatory practices on the basis of origin of Latin American migrants in Spain in the field of job search, despite geographical origin not being included as a protected variable in the Employment Equality Directive, which only refers to racial or ethnic origin.

In addition to EU law there are other non-EU bodies and organizations that currently work to protect people against discrimination like the Steering Committee on Anti-Discrimination, Diversity and Inclusion (CDADI) supports the intergovernmental work of the Council of Europe. At the Federal level in the United States, the Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights issued by the White House in October 2022 shares a set of algorithmic discrimination protections (White House 2022), which together with the most recent Executive Order on Safe, Secure and Trustworthy AI from October 30th, 2023 (White House 2023), constitute an initial effort to specifically address discrimination originated by automated systems. Moreover, the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission of the US (EEOC) has recently issued guidance on how to assess the adverse impact in software, algorithms and artificial intelligence used in employment selection procedures under title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964, based on the famous four fifths (80%) rule (EEOC 2023). At the city level, the City of New York issued Local Law 144 of 2021 (The New York City Council 2021), also known as the anti-bias law, that requires employers to audit human resources systems for bias (individual and group disparities) and publish their results, which took effect on January 1st, 2023 (NYC: Consumer and Worker Protection 2023). While some overseas efforts might not necessarily apply to use cases in Spain, they speak to a broader international trend that places great importance in the

prevention of discrimination through the use of machine learning algorithms, and in some instances in particular for the employment sector.

Despite these efforts, recent research warns about the unintended consequences of a strictly legal/regulatory approach towards discrimination. Ovalle for instance highlights how anti-discrimination law informs the design and research of AI-based systems that might see racial discrimination not as “conditions” but as “actions” inflicted on the victim by the perpetrator”. According to Ovalle, paraphrasing research of David Freeman in 1977 on legitimizing racial discrimination through anti-discrimination law, the fact that regulation focuses on “actions” might create the effect that only “intentional” discrimination violates anti-discrimination law, thus freeing from responsibility those who abide by acceptable thresholds like the 80% rule (Ovalle et al. 2023), legitimizing the remaining 20% of discriminated groups or individuals. In this sense, one of the major challenges for anti-discrimination law is to adequately address the dynamics of discrimination through the use of machine learning algorithms, which might be infected at several entry points like the coding or actual formalization of a problem in mathematical terms and the data it uses as inputs for the system (Xenidis and Senden 2020). Another issue stemming from the relatively incipient nature of the analysis of AI/ML and discrimination is the lack of common definitions and metrics about what accounts for a discriminatory practice. Research by Sandra Wachter at the Oxford Internet Institute shows how contextual definitions are about fairness in response to social and political dynamics (Wachter, Mittelstadt, and Russell 2020). This discussion is relevant for this report, as it pinpoints the main challenges on the application of non-discrimination regulation versus taking a broader ethics perspective where the aim is not only compliance with legal requirements, rather the proactive attitude of building better, more inclusive and trustworthy technology.

1.4 Conclusion

Enhancing the current quantitative research on algorithmic discrimination in hiring requires a deeper exploration of the socio-technical dynamics inherent in the algorithms' application in this domain. This nuanced approach goes beyond quantitative analysis, shedding light on the perspectives driving decisions and design choices in the development of products and services that may inadvertently introduce biases and discrimination against specific groups. Critical theory and intersectionality provide valuable insights into how vulnerable groups perceive the benefits of these technologies in their job searches, offering a granular understanding. Moreover, this report includes an intersectional approach, which considers the viewpoints of users (such as migrants), developers, and recruiters, all crucial in comprehensively evaluating the overall impact of this technology. Additionally, this report scrutinizes the implications of adopting a legal and regulatory perspective on discrimination versus embracing a broader ethical framework that transcends mere compliance, aiming to foster the development of more trustworthy and equitable algorithmic systems.

Section 2: Methodology

2.1 Mixed Methods, Communicative Methodology (CM) and Design Thinking (DT)

Based on the theoretical framework, this expert report employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods along with social engagement to obtain practical insights and issue actionable recommendations to a specific audience including developers, recruiters, policy makers and job seekers. This report also aims at informing the work of the FINDHR project with a sound theoretical framework and methodological rigor to be comparable to other expert reports conducted in parallel to this work.

The used methodology aims at assessing the technologies employed by online platforms, which range from mere statistical methods and data analytics tools to AI/ML-based models, and understand how they might affect migrants from Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain. This methodology also aims at obtaining a broader picture from a socio-technical perspective on how algorithmic fairness and non-discrimination might be compromised under certain conditions, assessing the perceptions of the abovementioned group of people, as well as the perspectives of developers and recruiting companies to provide more informed recommendations. The mixed-methods approach includes field work through the use of focus groups, individual interviews and a survey to understand the perspectives on algorithmic fairness and non-discrimination in hiring from all three groups involved in this process. This mixed-methods approach will include pattern identification through recurring themes related to the perception of discrimination based on protected attributes.

This analytical effort is guided by a communicative methodology (CM) approach that allows for the implementation of evidence-based policies to improve people's lives. Inspired by theories and methods developed in other paradigms and rooted in dialogue, CM has become a solid methodological framework that researchers can put into practice (Gómez, Elboj, and Capllonch, 2013). This report finds crucial to establish egalitarian dialogic interactions with members of society who participate in the research, allowing the research team to co-create knowledge together with the participants. The researchers of this report contribute with empirical knowledge to the dialogue, while social actors contribute by describing and reflecting on their life experiences. The final results are geared towards transforming society through actions based on this jointly developed evidence, to be applied to the use of machine learning algorithms in hiring and job search practices.

Additionally, this methodology includes a design thinking approach, which is a technique that allows one to focus on the needs of people, in this case migrants (McLaughlin, Wolcott, and Hubbard. et al., 2019). The process considers both the socio-ethical and technological aspects to ensure that the proposed recommendations are viable and sustainable. This approach is an iterative and non-linear process that encourages collaboration between researchers and social

actors. In this sense, this report emphasizes the importance of continuous feedback and iteration throughout the process. This flexible process allowed the researchers of this report to revisit and refine previous stages based on new insights gained through emergent feedback.

In accordance with GDPR compliance and due to the sensitivity of this topic, names in this report have been changed to preserve the anonymity of the participants. The real names, pictures and identifiable data is preserved by the research team.

The following table explains how the theoretical framework informs the methodology design for this report and explains what are the most relevant research questions addressed by theoretical framework and methodology. Nonetheless, it is important to highlight that given the intricate relationship among all concepts, these are ultimately embedded into each of the research questions.

Table 1. Conceptual map and relationship between theoretical framework and methodology.

Theoretical framework	Main theoretical concepts	Conceptual integration into methodology	Relevant research questions
Social Theory and the Internet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socio-technical perspective. - Narratives (technological determinism versus social determinism). - Non-neutrality of technology. - Directed technological change. - Algorithmic fairness and non-discrimination. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying the challenges and opportunities that migrants face when interacting with AI/ML-based systems in hiring. - Understanding the visions and narratives behind technological development and deployment. - Consulting with relevant actors in the hiring process including migrants, developers and recruiters. - Situating algorithmic fairness in the hiring process. - Mapping the different stages of job search and impact for migrants. 	<p>Research question 1: Use of machine learning algorithms in the hiring process</p> <p>Research question 3: Views, challenges and opportunities to develop trustworthy solutions</p>
Critical Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intersectionality. - Positionality. - Situated knowledge. - Epistemic communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding how personal characteristics combined with the migration process has an impact on the overall job search experience. - Highlighting the fact that overlapping disadvantages create a significantly different experience in 	<p>Research question 2: Perceived effects of the use of machine learning algorithms in</p>

		<p>the use of technology for hiring.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessing the epistemological gaps among migrants, developers and recruiters. - Evaluating potential for discrimination in the use of technology for hiring. 	<p>terms of fairness and non-discrimination</p>
Anti-discrimination Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discrimination law and obligations. - Impact of regulatory approaches on non-discrimination. - Anti-discrimination in the use of AI/ML. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping out relevant regulations on non-discrimination in Europe and Spain. - Understanding the implications of non-discrimination law for the use of AI/ML in hiring. 	<p>Research question 2: Perceived effects of the use of machine learning algorithms in terms of fairness and non-discrimination</p>

Figure 1. Timeline of the project

2.1.1 Research questions

Based on the theoretical framework and methodological approaches, this report aims at addressing the following questions through the establishment of dedicated sections that

inform: 1. How are algorithms used for hiring? 2. How do people perceive these tools have an impact on them in terms of fairness and non-discrimination? and 3. What are the views and perceptions of developers and recruiters on the fairness and non-discrimination aspects in the deployment of these technologies? These three main questions are expanded below:

Research question 1 - Use of machine learning algorithms in the hiring process

1. At what stages of the hiring process does algorithmic fairness and non-discrimination is perceived to be at odds by migrants from Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain?
 - a. What is the landscape of automation and use of AI-based systems in the hiring process in Spain?
 - b. What kind of AI-based systems are developed and used by companies throughout the hiring process?

Research question 2 - Perceived effects of the use of machine learning algorithms in terms of fairness and non-discrimination

2. How do intersecting characteristics of origin, gender, race, education, and socioeconomic standing, interact and create unique forms of algorithmic interaction?
 - a. What are the specific (online and offline) challenges these overlapping categories face when interacting with online platforms? Offline challenges refer to offline features that pose difficulties for the person to search for jobs online (e.g. lack of digital literacy, lack of mobile devices or Internet).
 - b. What are the key design features of the online hiring platforms that are perceived to be the most unfair to the above-mentioned group?

Research question 3 - Views, challenges and opportunities to develop trustworthy solutions

3. How innovative strategies, visions and narratives could be harnessed to promote the development of robust, inclusive and trustworthy online platforms for hiring?
 - a. What are the main obstacles for firms (developers and users) to identify, prevent, mitigate or correct known unfair outcomes of algorithms in the hiring process?
 - b. What are the key dynamics behind the tech-innovation ecosystem that hinder the incorporation of ethical approaches in the development of their products and services?

2.1.2 Field work

As mentioned before, this report based its field work on two-in person focus groups with migrant women in the cities of Bilbao and Barcelona, one survey directed to migrant women, one-to-one interviews with migrants and specialists at the intersection of migration,

employment, technology and rights, and one online focus group with private sector entities and the participation of C-level executives and data scientists.

2.1.2.1 Target groups (methodology)

The main target group of this report are migrants from Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain that use online hiring platforms, which is the group potentially subject to algorithmic discrimination. As stated in the methodology, the research analyzes how this group perceives that offline and online tools and practices affect their opportunities for employment. The secondary target group encompasses two different actors from the private sector, which are the developer companies of the online platforms and some representatives of companies using the services of the online platforms in one or more stages of their recruitment and selection process. The latter group is in charge of the automation of certain tasks in the hiring process prone to algorithmic discrimination. The insights of this group are relevant to understand what are the possible avenues for the development of more inclusive, robust and trustworthy technologies in the hiring sector.

2.1.2.2 Outreach strategy (methodology)

One of the most challenging aspects of this research was to obtain the participation of migrants, who face significant difficulties in their daily lives to devote time to participate in this kind of research activities, as well as from developers and recruiters who also face a heavy workload with apparently few incentives to participate in this kind of consultations. However, the research team, with the support of members of the FINDHR consortium were able to engage with 36 members and representatives of civil society organizations working to support migrants, networks of migrants and professionals from Latin America, industry associations of technology providers, startups, scaleups, and recruiters. This led in turn to the participation of 7 migrants in two focus groups that took place in Barcelona and Bilbao in early October 2023, as well as 5 industry participants in an online focus group in late October. In addition, this allowed for the reception of 24 responses of the survey for migrants.

In order to reach the first target group, i.e. migrants from Latin America seeking for employment in Spain, the research team contacted a number of civil society organizations (CSOs), based on two main criteria: From a functional perspective, CSOs that work on direct social intervention (counseling, job search advisory, country arrival support, among others), and with a local grassroots base. From a socio-demographics perspective, CSOs that regularly engage with migrant women from Latin American countries, which had faced complexities to find a job in Spain upon their arrival, regardless of their attained level of education, their current job situation, and their documentation status. In order to proceed with a diverse set of participants, the group undertook online meetings with representatives from NGOs in Barcelona, Bilbao (the two target cities for Focus Groups) and Madrid. The group approached both constituted NGOs as well as grassroots groups of migrant women that convened to exchange their personal, professional, and family issues with a focus on integration.

The team of researchers leveraged its network of contacts in key civil society organizations and universities to reach gatekeepers, representatives and interested participants. The proposal was to create a basic flier and conduct face-to-face meetings and/or online meetings to inform about the purpose, scope and value of the research to foster participation.

The second target group, i.e. developers and recruiters, was contacted mainly through industry associations of companies working in the development of digital technologies, in particular for the selection, recruitment and job advertisement sector. The analysis of the attitudes and internal processes of private sector entities on the usage and uptake of machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms for hiring decisions is one of the main axes of analysis in this project. The research has devoted efforts to two aspects. First, based on background information, it assesses the evidence-based information on how businesses and corporations design, frame, develop, and deploy AI in hiring. Second, the research group has developed a Focus Group with representatives from firms that are either (1) using AI in their hiring processes, or (2) where AI is the core element of the business because it is the technological connector, bridge, between providers and clients for a specific service (e.g. matching services to find employees).

2.1.2.3 Platform analysis (methodology)

This section was intended to map out the main online platforms throughout the hiring process, including job posting, profiling, ranking and shortlisting of candidates and applicants, interviewing tools and predicting the future performance of candidates in their job positions. Section 3, which primarily deals in the assessment of the technologies deployed illustrates the main type of technologies used in the hiring process, as well as the main challenges and current efforts to develop trustworthy technology. This section was informed primarily by an online focus group with participants of an industry association, startups developing and deploying machine-learning and artificial intelligence for hiring, one in particular for migrants seeking for employment. Participation was highly informative and valuable, which included the active participation of 5 highly qualified professionals throughout the entire focus group of C-level executives like Chief Artificial Intelligence Officer, Chief Technology and Product Officers, and data scientists.

2.1.2.4 Perceptions of migrants (methodology)

Section 4 of this report aims at understanding the perceptions of the affected group about the use of the online platform hiring systems and what are the main barriers (online and offline) that might be directly impeding access to equal opportunity employment. To do this, the research team of this report elaborated a survey, conducted two focus groups and elaborated 6 one-to-one interviews, whose results are shown in the correspondent section.

Based on this aggregate and anonymous responses, section 4 combines the insights from the interviews with the information collected during the focus groups in Barcelona and Bilbao

with the participation of 7 migrants, all women both from professional and non-professional backgrounds.

Section 3: Platform analysis and technology assessment

In 2023, job seekers in Spain make use of a variety of platforms, ranging from well-known international websites like LinkedIn and Indeed to national platforms such as MilAnuncios and InfoJobs. Additionally, the country's public employment service SEPE (Servicio Público de Empleo Estatal) provides online platforms for both job seekers and employers. While these platforms share the common objective of connecting applicants with job opportunities, they vary in several key aspects. Differences include the algorithms used to recommend jobs, the range and specificity of job listings, and even the filtering mechanisms in place for sensitive content.

To enhance user experience, these platforms employ various forms of automation. Although the specific algorithms are typically not publicly disclosed, they commonly feature recommendation systems to suggest personalized job opportunities, search algorithms designed to find optimal results for specific queries, matching algorithms that pair job seekers with suitable positions, and ranking algorithms that prioritize the most relevant content. Additionally, some platforms require users to manually input their professional data, while others utilize *curriculum* parsing methods to automatically populate numerous profile fields. These platforms continue to be the preferred choice for many job seekers, offering practical means to explore job listings, engage with recruiters, and connect with peers in their respective fields.

Nevertheless, relying on these platforms brings forth challenges, notably the lack of control over the information utilized for profile matching and the limitation of involving job-seekers in certain aspects of the recruitment process. This marks a distance from the more flexible and human-centered approach that was prevalent before the surge in popularity of these tools. To tackle these challenges effectively, there is a pressing need for the development of systems that adhere to trustworthy AI principles. This challenge necessitates the collaborative efforts of various stakeholders, including policymakers, project managers, and AI developers, to establish guidelines and regulations that advocate for the responsible utilization of AI technology within the employment sector.

Currently, national governments and international organizations are taking proactive measures to enforce mandatory regulations pertaining to trustworthy AI, such as developing national AI strategies and international frameworks for AI systems. These policies outline guidelines for ensuring trustworthiness at every stage of the AI lifecycle, with the goal of mitigating associated issues. While significant efforts are underway in the most industrialized and technologically advanced countries, governments continue to face challenges in effectively implementing national AI strategies within domestic businesses.

3.1. Uses of AI technology in the hiring process

In the realm of hiring, technology has revolutionized efficiency across various stages. Automated resume review tools, for instance, streamline the process by analyzing resumes, saving recruiters valuable time otherwise spent on repetitive tasks like searching for structured information typically found in sections titled "education" and "work experience," often underlined and immutable. Another instance of automation in hiring involves the use of competency tests supported by online platforms, offering objective insights into applicants' skills. Furthermore, data analytics tools play a relevant role by providing actionable insights into hiring patterns, enabling companies to fine-tune their strategies. By integrating these technologies, companies ensure smooth operations and optimize their hiring processes. They leverage data-driven decisions to maintain competitiveness in the ever-evolving market landscape.

One of the most common applications of AI in hiring is utilizing machine learning tools to assess whether a candidate aligns with a specific job post, their likelihood of staying in the position if selected, and their potential success in the role. These initial automated results are predetermined by a trained model, relying on input data known as training data. Also, models may or may not have been tested against unknown data to validate their accuracy and reliability in making inferences about unknown data.

Thus, the hiring process, a multifaceted journey spanning from job posting to interviewing, demands meticulous navigation. It encompasses crafting compelling job descriptions, actively sourcing candidates, creating precise profiles, and employing nuanced ranking and shortlisting methods. Each step involves a delicate balance between evaluating qualifications and assessing cultural fit within the organization.

In order to assess the technologies currently being used by AI stakeholders in the Spanish labor market, an online workshop was carried out with IT professionals in different fields of activity. In this session, a remote focus group was carried out in order to understand their perception of AI algorithms in the hiring process, as well as the challenges that they face when deploying such technologies, as well as the efforts to currently deploy trustworthiness to their AI pipelines. The following table summarizes the AI solutions that were mentioned by these professionals during the online workshop.

Table 2. Main types of digital technologies employed in the hiring process as seen through the lens of the consulted population, which mostly interacts with job search platforms

AI technology	Description
Named entity recognition	Named entity recognition (NER) and semantic analysis play important roles in resume parsing, enabling the extraction of meaningful information like skills and experiences from unstructured resumes. These advanced techniques

	enhance the accuracy and efficiency of matching this extracted data with structured fields, streamlining the hiring process significantly.
Generative AI	Generative AI can be employed to create job descriptions and to ensure that they are unbiased and non-discriminatory. It can also be used to generate high-quality resumes based on conversations and third-party information.
Enhanced user interaction	Chatbots enable conversational interaction for applicants, allowing them to find information through dialogue rather than traditional search methods. They can also conduct initial conversations to gate candidates for further evaluation, further validated by human assessment.
Skills and experience matching	ML can be used to predict the types of jobs needed to complete a project, ensuring appropriate staffing (e.g., developers or designers).
Predictive analytics	Predictive models determine the best time and method to post job listings based on specific regions and segments. They can also predict culture fit and talent/project engagement.
Ranking and profiling	Candidates' job experiences and profiles are preprocessed into a structured data format, with predefined features, which can then be used to train an algorithm. The resulting outputs typically involve ranking candidates based on their likelihood of fitting a specific job position.
Recommendation systems	Job recommendations are generated for both candidates and employers, using a multi-stage recommendation system. Recommendations are tailored specifically to individual skills and requirements.
Sentiment analysis	Speech-to-text and summarization are used to analyze post-interview transcripts and assess candidate suitability. Sentiment analysis is applied to cover letters and interview transcripts to identify specific emotions.
Churn prediction	Churn prediction models are utilized to evaluate the probability of employees leaving the organization in the upcoming months or years.
Two-sided matching and Game theory	By aligning preferences and strategic interaction, two-sided stable matching and Game theory principles optimize candidate-employer pairings, ensuring mutual satisfaction and long-term retention.

According to the OECD, the AI life cycle comprises key stages: "Build and interpret model", "Collect and process data", "Deploy", "Operate and monitor", "Plan and design", and "Verify and validate" (*OECD Framework for the Classification of AI Systems* 2019). While most discussed AI technologies pertain to the initial stage, others are applicable in other stages, such as data collection and processing. Evaluating trustworthiness is a collective task spanning the entire pipeline. For example, if AI is implemented during model building, assessing fairness must encompass input data balance, feature weighting, and real-world data inference after a proper model training. Furthermore, challenges arise in testing algorithms for specific positions due to

limited suitable sources, often leading to prioritizing model deployment over real-world performance assessment in hiring decisions.

Moreover, challenges arise due to the complex nature of human skills and workplace dynamics. Algorithms must contend with subtle human interactions, striving to accurately quantify them. Ethical concerns, including mitigating bias and ensuring data privacy, pose significant issues. For example, the process of scaling and transforming data to eliminate bias is not obligatory in running a machine learning pipeline itself. Models can be trained on any set of input features, whether they are balanced or not, and are often crafted to mimic results in a target variable. Generally, if a model is trained on balanced and unbiased features, it should not exhibit biased behavior when tested with these features.

Finally, the challenges that come with training, deploying and using AI systems in any of stages of the AI lifecycle were also mentioned in the focus groups with the migrant women. It turned out that most of them did not have any significant experience with the interactions of any algorithmic system beyond job postings, but did agree that their data could be misused given their lack of technical knowledge on the subject.

3.2. Main challenges to develop trustworthy solutions

While there are many directions that a given AI solution can take in order to better implement trustworthiness, such as focusing on increasing privacy or reducing bias, the professionals who participated in the online workshop mentioned that technical knowledge and expertise in AI is usually required to properly embed changes into these complex systems. For instance, the choice for algorithms affects future understanding of their functioning. Deep learning architectures are becoming more popular than before, given the increase in open-source platforms to make them available, such as Hugging Face, and given the latest developments in state-of-the-art tasks related to several AI-related subfields, such as NLP and Computer vision. While the usage of traditional machine learning architectures such as random forest and logistic regressors are still popularly used thanks to their easy and inexpensive usage, these models are much more limited in terms of generalization given their architectures. Deep learning models, on the other hand, are more promising in terms of generalization, given that their architectures allow for more nonlinear calculations and regularization techniques to limit overfitting are more flexible and effective. While being more advanced and generalizable AI architectures, a proper understanding of their functioning is mandatory in order to assure trustworthiness in these systems. Commonly called “black-box” models, deep learning architectures such as recurrent neural networks and convolutional networks are widely employed nowadays, from face recognition in smartphones to large language models. In the online workshop, the difficulty in assessing explainability while using these “black-box” models, regardless of constant efforts to assess correctness in their data and models, was mentioned as one of the biggest challenges in assessing trustworthiness in the AI solutions they use.

This challenge also piles up with data scarcity. Some professionals mentioned that their business aims at matching candidates with job postings, but oftentimes the data provided by

the candidates is incomplete, missing or inaccurate. Thus, they must assess this limitation in the “data collection” phase of the AI lifecycle in order to help these candidates fill their CVs properly before automation. One of the companies developed an innovative recommendation system for job matching, while being a small start-up. They leveraged advanced recommendation algorithms, drawing inspiration from game theory. Their algorithm analyzes various facets of talent and client profiles, ensuring that the recommendations are not just relevant but also tailored to specific needs and preferences, enhancing the overall user experience. Nevertheless, it was mentioned that data is their main limitation, given that every new feature added to their solution would imply a new data collection from users for that specific feature. Thus, including such a feature in their machine learning algorithm requires a decent amount of data that should be general enough.

Moreover, other professionals focused on talent and client verification, emphasizing the art of precise matching. By delving into the intricacies of their verification process, these companies ensure a trustworthy environment for both talent and clients. For some of them, their platform's commitment to thorough verification not only enhances credibility but also fosters a sense of security for all stakeholders involved.

In the following table, the key challenges faced and mentioned by the participants in the online webinar are listed.

Table 3. List of challenges faced by machine learning systems in hiring to avoid bias and discrimination.

Challenge	Description
Data collection	Companies struggle with collecting diverse and relevant data for their use cases. While attempts to generate diversity are made through interviews, it is oftentimes still far from being optimal. The size of the data that can be collected can still be too limited, leading to potential gaps in the dataset.
Data quality	Limited and self-generated data from users might be an initial limitation in the AI lifecycle. The data collected from clients might be too specific and not representative of diverse communities, which can lead to biased outcomes in AI algorithms. A lower quality of the data might be due to it being too small, as it often happens for small and medium enterprises, or because the data is too expensive to be obtained by traditional retrieval techniques.
Algorithm testing	Testing involves human evaluation, moving beyond relying solely on algorithms. This can be a limitation if there is a lack of a good test dataset that represents real-world scenarios.
Explainability and transparency	Focus on explaining the level of algorithmic explainability and promoting transparency in AI models. “Black-box” models are still too hard to explain given the expertise needed, and trustworthy AI-related issues might become

	challenging to mitigate without a proper understanding of the detailed internal functioning of the algorithm architecture.
Lack of maturity in AI solutions	Some aspects of AI solutions, like interviewing and speech recognition, lack maturity in many companies. Companies might be using AI technologies without a deep understanding of their limitations and biases.
Privacy and data governance	Balancing the need for transparency with preserving confidentiality and sensitive information of individuals is a challenge that companies face in implementing trustworthy AI.

In the online workshop, unanimity existed when mentioning challenges in data representation and distribution, given that some of these companies are small to medium-sized, which limited a good demographic representation of the data to be used. One of the challenges existed in the phase of development of a new feature, given that new data is gathered for that specific feature, which already poses a limitation from start given that the data obtained by small companies might be too small to be correctly representing a target group. Thus, technical procedures to cope with these limitations must be addressed at early stages, such as the usage of data augmentation techniques to create synthetic data for hard-to-obtain data, or even expensive data, usually inaccessible to smaller businesses (more details in the next Subsection).

Furthermore, complying with national and international regulatory changes pose a problem as new policies and general AI guidelines are being developed in parallel with the businesses. Not only the current machine learning model in production from businesses must comply with current national and international regulations of data usage and correctness, but it should also be attentive to new adaptations that are being made to the existing ones. For instance, many AI national strategies have been focusing and prioritizing developing new guidelines and restrictions for the usage of generative AI within their borders. Countries are adapting to the emergence of generative AI by emphasizing international cooperation, policy frameworks, and stakeholder engagement. The need for fostering local AI innovation through international collaboration, representative datasets, AI expertise, responsible policy frameworks, and data protection is constantly highlighted. Emphasis is placed on involving diverse stakeholders in AI governance, including governments, private companies, and civil society, underscoring the necessity for governments to respond to rapid AI advancements and engage with diverse stakeholders to comprehend the societal and sectoral impacts of these technologies (*G7 Hiroshima Process on Generative Artificial Intelligence 2023*).

3.3. Current efforts to develop trustworthy technology

In 2019, the "OECD Framework for the Classification of AI Systems" was published, serving as a reference of guidance on categorizing artificial intelligence (AI) systems based on their technical features. This framework supports policymakers and researchers in classifying AI systems for purposes like policy analysis and international comparison. It provides a systematic

approach considering technical aspects, functionalities, and applications. The framework includes the different criteria associated with AI systems, methodologies, and discussions on challenges in establishing a standardized AI classification system. The OECD AI Principles promote use of AI that is innovative and trustworthy and that respects human rights and democratic values, and sets standards for AI that are practical and flexible enough to stand the test of time. They are: **“Accountability”, “Fairness”, “Human wellbeing”, “Performance”, “Privacy and data governance”, “Robustness and digital security”, “Safety”** and **“Transparency and explainability”** (OECD Framework for the Classification of AI Systems 2019).

In the contemporary hiring landscape, the call for fairness and transparency resonates profoundly. It is being increasingly required for companies to champion these values at every hiring stage, recognizing the societal demand for equal opportunities. In the pursuit of a nuanced understanding of the complexities in the hiring process, the participants in the online workshop engaged in an interactive session where they placed sticky notes on a process map, delineating the various stages and challenges intertwined with technology. This exercise illustrated the intricate journey of hiring, from job posting to prediction. From automated resume screening to video interviews, the mapping showcased the diverse array of challenges faced. This collaborative exercise not only fostered shared insights but also provided an interactive platform for them to engage deeply with the evolving role of automation in shaping the future of recruitment. The main findings are depicted in the following table.

Table 4. Efforts undertaken by AI professionals to foster inclusion and non-discrimination in their technologies deployed in the hiring process.

Effort	Description
Data augmentation	Synthetic data and statistical methods are employed to address data challenges.
Diversity enhancement	Attempts are made to generate diversity through interviews, particularly focusing on underrepresented communities like women developers.
Implementation of regularization techniques	Regularization is needed in order to reduce the risk of overfitting a given model, which occurs when a model does not generalize enough. This can be done both on the data side by refraining from putting overly specific data into production to prevent overfitting issues, and on the model size, by using regularization techniques such as dropout.
Transparency initiatives	Transparency is emphasized, with companies aiming to publish information, research, and model architectures. There are efforts to make results public to address non-discrimination concerns.
Regulatory compliance	Companies are preparing for European regulations, including GDPR and the EU AI Act, emphasizing transparency and compliance.

Cultural considerations

Acknowledgment of the importance of local adaptation and understanding cultural differences in the hiring process.

Additionally to the online workshop findings, risk-management frameworks can be integrated alongside the AI system lifecycle to promote trustworthy AI. One example is the report on governing and managing risks throughout the AI lifecycle, which contains technical and process-related approaches to mitigate harms associated with the OECD AI principles (*Advancing accountability in AI: Governing and managing risks throughout the lifecycle for trustworthy AI* 2023).

Other efforts exist in terms of metrics and tools associated with trustworthy AI. Currently, more than 600 tools and 100 metrics exist in the Catalog of Tools and Metrics for Trustworthy AI, which is a platform created by the OECD to make available existing solutions for all types of stakeholders (OECD Catalog of Tools and Metrics for Trustworthy AI 2023). In the employment sector, it includes guidelines, checklists and other types of assessment that can help employers, companies, management teams and policy makers, among others, to develop best practices in hiring. For instance, private solutions such as BABL AI conducts third-party audits for automated employment decision tools. Ethical AI frameworks such as the six standards for managing the ethical deployment of AI in hiring developed by Modern Hire can also guide HR teams to best implement trustworthiness into their selection processes. There are also frameworks to act as a roadmap for businesses to design, procure and use AI to benefit and not discriminate against qualified individuals with disabilities, such as the US Employer Assistance and Resource Network on Disability Inclusion.

As mentioned previously, there is a considerable difference between complying with legislation and proactively advocating for trustworthiness. Given the lack of a more thorough and solid framework to measure and mitigate issues that can harm any of the AI principles, setting benchmarks for assessing trustworthiness within a given system is a challenging task. On the other hand, all companies that participated in the online session developed and included tools within their AI models that, to a given extent, assess how trustworthy at least one of the AI principles were. In terms of current efforts, an AI index is needed to quantitatively assess and scale trustworthy AI.

One of the main conclusions is a mismatch between the initial hypothesis and the final results derived from the different stages of the hiring process. This section was originally intended to map out the main online platforms throughout the hiring process, including job posting, profiling, ranking and shortlisting of candidates and applicants, interviewing tools and predicting the future performance of candidates in their job positions. However, after conducting field work, it turned out that most of the participants consulted in the survey, focus groups and interviews did not have any significant experience with the interactions of any algorithmic system beyond job postings. Consultations revealed that migrants tend to follow a path of hardship that impedes them to easily become part of the regular workforce, thus getting less opportunity to engage with more sophisticated Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS),

used by larger companies or corporations. Instead, the group of migrants we interacted with mostly used social media platforms, job posting websites, and the corporate websites of companies and NGOs advertising job positions.

Section 4: Perceptions of affected groups

In addition to the analysis conducted on IT professionals in different fields, as part of our research to assess the impact of technologies on Latin American women migrants seeking employment in the Spanish labor market, we explore the following questions: How do the intersecting characteristics of origin, gender, race, education, and socioeconomic standing interact to create distinctive forms of algorithmic interaction? What specific challenges, both online and offline, do individuals within these overlapping categories encounter when engaging with online platforms? And finally, what are the primary design features of online hiring platforms that are perceived as particularly unfair to this aforementioned group?

To respond to these questions, the following analysis is drawn from two focus groups in Bilbao and Barcelona, and a survey that was shared online with anonymous response. In order to give an outlook on the type of respondents of the latter, we have included their main socio-demographic features.

Twentyfour responses to the survey were received with participants from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Mexico, Nicaragua, Peru, Uruguay and Venezuela with an age range between 31 and 61 years old. Most participants self-identified as female (75%) and the rest as male (25%), even though other non-binary forms of identification were offered in the survey. Half of participants already hold dual citizenship and the other half are nationals from their own countries with long-term residency permission (17%), temporary residency (8%), or student visa (8%). The minority of respondents (8%) mentioned being under irregular migration conditions or “other” migratory status.

In terms of academic background, the highest academic degree obtained by respondents was: College/University (11: 46%), Postgraduate (10: 42%), Technical Degree (1: 4%) and Secondary school (1: 4%). In terms of years of professional experience, 33% have 3 to 5 years, 29% 5 to 10 years, 21% 10 to 20 years, and 13% more than 20 years. In terms of the main industries where respondents work, results were: 33% consulting and other professional workers, 29% in services, 17% in NGOs, 8% in government, and 8% in industry. In terms of their current employment situation, 33% mentioned to be employed with permanent contracts, 25% to be employed with fixed term contracts, 25% to be independent or autonomous workers, 13% to be unemployed, and 4% to have a family business.

4.1. Perceptions of online platforms

In the context of the participants, vulnerability is a prominent theme that crosses several aspects in the different job search experiences with the different online platforms. Regarding

the survey and focus groups, the first way to search is *online platforms*, second *networks* and third *mobile apps*. The overall satisfaction with tools is 3.10 out of 5 perceived 2.67 out of 5 of effectiveness and 3.09 out of 5 of familiarity and ease of use of the platforms.

Figure 2: Question 10. Main ways to look for employment

● Newspaper job offers	3
● Internet and platforms	16
● Mobile apps	7
● University websites and networks	3
● Temporary job ads agencies	1
● State or government service	2
● Professional or personal networks	10
● Direct contact with the company or business	5
● Open calls	2
● Establishing own business	1
● Other	2

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

Figure 3: Question 12. Overall satisfaction with tools. 3.05/5.00 average

3.05
Average Score

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

Figure 4: Question 13. Effectiveness perceived to search for a job. 2.64/5.00 average

2.64
Average Score

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

Figure 5: Question 14. Familiarity and ease of use of the platforms. 3.09/5.00 average

3.09
Average Score

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

As we describe in the next sections, the results from the survey, interviews and focus groups indicated that it is essential that companies take into account the different profiles and experiences from users, which require special care in their development tools, to avoid bias and violations of Human Rights as equality of treatment, privacy and ensure the safety and proper use of the platforms. The “socio-technical capital” plays a key role in the equity in the use, benefits and appropriation of technologies by individuals, so there must be a consideration regarding inclusiveness and transparency, taking into account the different levels of digital and educational training.

Mil Anuncios generates skepticism among consulted participants due to issues of truthfulness and reluctance to share personal information. InfoJobs¹ (<https://www.infojobs.net/>) is perceived by consulted participants as lacking clear explanations for unsuccessful candidates, which generates frustration and confusion. Companies should be transparent throughout the entire selection and employment process. Users need to know at which stage their application stands and why they have been rejected if that is the case. Transparency helps build trust and clarity in job-related interactions. *Adecco* (<https://www.adecco.es/>) stands out for its non-automated processes that require a lot of time and resources from participants, but also faces complications when working with specific clients. *TopNanny* (<https://topnanny.net/>), according to some participants, faces challenges such as lack of communication with employers due to lack of transparency and a cumbersome application process. Facebook and WhatsApp are well received among almost all consulted participants for basic work, but WhatsApp is mainly used for off-line communication. The main findings are depicted in the following table:

Table 5. Perceptions from surveyed migrants on ease and trustworthy to use online platforms for search job, and perceptions obtained in focus groups

Themes	Description
Mil Anuncios	The platform is viewed with skepticism by the interviewees due to issues of trust and security. There is reluctance to share personal information such as names and contact numbers. The platform also offers incentives for financial contributions to feature job postings, which raises concerns about fairness and transparency.
InfoJobs	The recruitment processes on InfoJobs lack clear explanations for candidates who are not selected. The system uses color codes as reference to indicate the status of the process but does not provide specific details about rejections, leading to frustration and confusion among users. The platform is perceived as having low reliability.
Adecco	Adecco's processes involve non-automated interviews and video calls that are time-consuming. These processes include surveys and detailed explanations for digital assessments. Adecco collaborates with specific clients like Amazon, especially for roles that demand technical skills and the ability to record responses in a specific environment. This environment can often be challenging for the interviewees to find, impacting their ability to conduct interviews effectively due to issues like lack of space, connectivity and quiet areas.
TopNanny	Negative experiences were reported by users who mentioned challenges in finding employment through the platform, often due to misunderstandings with employers resulting from a lack of transparency in the service seekers' profiles. Additionally, the application process is time-consuming, requiring individual applications for each job offer. Some users found it uncomfortable to be asked

¹ InfoJobs is operated by Adeventa, a partner of FINDHR. It is relevant to address that Adeventa's representatives were not consulted for commentary nor participated in this research.

	to upload a photo, and there were instances where job postings favored local candidates.
Facebook	Users reported positive experiences when applying for catering jobs through Facebook. Notably, the platform's effectiveness extends beyond one's migrant status, as clients can see the user's profile and job offerings.
LinkedIn	LinkedIn is a specialized and professional platform with various application modes of application. 'Easy apply' were well-received by users for their fast and simple way, while the platform also has external websites, making the application process more cumbersome. Building a network of contacts and gaining visibility is crucial on LinkedIn, requiring regular usage and exposure to ads. It's essential to maintain a well-defined profile to avoid receiving unrelated job offers.
WhatsApp	WhatsApp is primarily used for personal communication with known references or for subsequent contact with individuals who have made job-related posts.
InfoJobs	Users faced challenges when trying to upload photos on InfoJobs, as it required advanced platform knowledge, according to consulted participants. Some users found the platform to be impersonal, and there were difficulties in uploading photos.
Job Search Platforms	Concerns were expressed regarding the use of these platforms due to the absence of legal documentation, potential risks of sexual harassment in interactions with strangers lacking references, phone call scams, and requests for excessive personal information such as fixed addresses and registration data. The use of multiple interfaces on both mobile and computer platforms to input information for different platforms, as seen in major consulting firms, was identified as a technological challenge. Additionally, concerns were raised regarding GDPR compliance and the acceptance of terms that users may not fully understand.

4.2. Offline barriers: Main barriers

The intersection of various characteristics contributes to the perception of discrimination among job interviews. These intersecting factors that occur outside of the digital realm or outside the internet and web applications is what this report denominates "offline", including aspects such as a lack of access to services, limited Internet access, lack of mobile devices, regulatory hurdles for non-formal job earnings, regional language requirements, bias and profiling in job registration, and challenges related to bringing their diplomas, collectively create a high risk of vulnerability in the users. The outcomes result in either facilitating or hindering individuals' employment prospects, often rooted in their legal status and background. For example, the inaccessibility of banking services and the difficulties in obtaining financial stability due to discrimination can severely limit employment opportunities to not use online platforms and to be excluded from job offers and accessing only precarious risk situations.

Additionally, regional language requirements and profiling based on residence can further exacerbate inequalities, resulting in exclusion from job processes and unequal compensation, mostly in the public sector. These findings emphasize the importance of addressing these socio-technical dynamics to ensure more equitable opportunities for all women migrants looking for jobs in the Spanish labor market.

In the following table, the key challenges faced and mentioned by the participants are listed:

Table 6. List of offline challenges faced by migrant women to search for employment opportunities

Themes	Description
Banking account	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extra costs, fees, discrimination due to origin. - Difficulties in opening bank accounts prevent them from receiving their salaries and hinder their employment prospects.
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some people earn money in non-formal jobs, as they do not have the documentation to work legally in Spain. - Many of the jobs offered are temporary, in poor conditions, and few permanent contracts are available due to document-related problems. This often leads to exploitation and precarious working conditions. Individuals who employ them, aware of their vulnerable status due to their legal situation, do not meet professional or personal standards. - Some interviewees mentioned working excessively long hours and a lack of regulation of their free time. For example, they reported working six days but being paid for only five because their employers knew they could not report due to their vulnerable situation or lack of proper documentation for regulation.
Regional languages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mostly in public employment, and also in some customer service jobs (private jobs), they require you to speak regional languages
Bias and Profiling Registration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviewees reported bias and profiling based on their place of residence, often due to their address, postal code, or information provided for registration. Sometimes, these factors lead to exclusion from job processes or lower compensation.
Certification and Diplomas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of knowledge about the importance of bringing diplomas from their home countries to Spain. - Fear of bringing the diplomas in the baggage, as they would be identified as suspect of staying illegally in Spain beyond the tourist visa timeframe. - Limitation in job opportunities, often confined to low-paying jobs and precarious conditions.

4.3. Online barriers

Based on the gathered information, it became evident that there are several significant findings concerning digital skills and challenges within the online job search environment. One crucial observation is the widespread lack of digital skills, which impedes women from effectively inputting information and utilizing digital tools to create online resumes (CVs). 62% of respondents expressed in the conducted survey that they believe they do not have access to sufficient support resources to find employment in Spain, exacerbating the inequality and hindering equal opportunities for women migrants.

Figure 6: Question 29. There are enough support resources to find employment

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

This digital skills gap extends to the use of job search platforms as well, the lack of infrastructure access. Furthermore, the interviews highlighted limited digital connectivity, marked by slow servers and restricted access to various platforms, which is a significant issue, especially for those primarily relying on mobile devices for job searches. Gender and intersectional bias in keyword searches further compound these challenges, potentially leading to the exclusion of certain profiles based on gender or other variables such as age, language, nationality, etc. The fear of lacking legal documentation, combined with concerns about scams, inappropriate messages, and online harassment, contributes to digital distrust, making it difficult for women to trust and effectively utilize online job platforms in their daily lives.

In addition, focus groups and surveys show that potential discriminatory practices related to women migrants from Latin America in Spain exist within the job search sphere. It is important to note that, while EU directives do not explicitly recognize discrimination based on geographical origin, they do acknowledge discrimination based on racial or ethnic origin. For example, the report highlights a case involving *Top Nanny*, where a candidate felt discriminated against based on her appearance, as the prospective employer preferred a local candidate. In this event, she was told that she looked too “latina” and that her skin was too dark. This underscores the importance of reviewing specific safeguards for geographical origin within algorithmic regulation, as discrimination based on countries of origin can occur and exacerbate issues related to ethnicity or language proficiency. For instance, some accents were reported as being considered inappropriate, and certain countries have negative stereotypes.

This was specifically mentioned by the Colombian and Venezuelan participants with respect to their own accents. According to one participant, the accent is a “first barrier when trying to search for new jobs”. In this context, there is a call for heightened awareness and measures to combat discrimination on online job platforms, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive and equitable job search environment.

One alarming issue that came to light is the exposure to and online sexual harassment reported by some of the interviewees. Several interviewees told us that from the information they posted on job search platforms they received inappropriate messages, photos, and sexual content. This aspect was mentioned by several interviewees. In the Focus Group in Bilbao, one participant stated that she was asked about her “weight, height, and waist and chest measurements”, and felt highly uncomfortable. In some cases, participants have seen online job offers where task descriptions include usual duties such as cleaning and care, but also other tasks such as sexual acts. They had different experiences of inappropriate harassment that even led them to stop using the platforms and prefer to work with contacts with references. They also said that it is very common that when they go to clean or do different tasks in homes, several men offer them to have more money for agreeing to sexual proposals. In one case, one of the participants said that she went to clean, and when she left the man hugged her and it was very uncomfortable, looking for other intentions, the next day she did not want to go and asked for her payment for the 8 hours of cleaning, and the man said he was not going to pay her. Therefore, they expressed that their vulnerability is high and these platforms contact them with people who have inadequate sharing, preferring contact through acquaintances to avoid these situations that arise from anonymity (in messages by telephone) or by not having references, contacts that provide guarantees.

This harassment often took the form of workplace harassment and online harassment, including sexual harassment encountered after contacting individuals through online job search platforms. Additionally, it extended to workplace harassment and phone harassment after the interviewees published their personal information on these platforms, which in many cases happened as sudden changes in the way the employer treated these women, inducing them to accept engaging in sexual-related activities for higher pay. As a result of these distressing experiences, many of them refrained from using online job search platforms out of fear of encountering inappropriate profiles once again. The lack of anonymity and inadequate reporting mechanisms were identified as significant problems for women to report these problems. Their vulnerability to job insecurity was exacerbated by the absence of stability and protection against harassment on online job platforms. Some participants indicated that they did not feel safe about “sending personal information such as personal addresses and whom they live with, because [they] do not know exactly if someone else may approach their houses”. Likewise, a representative from a grassroots organization that helps migrant women to find jobs, stated in a one-to-one interview that she was worried on whether “online platforms may sell the personal information that is shared during the job search process to insurance companies, or the fact that personal data may be kept by unlawful actors that steal information from these online platforms that are not 100% cyber-protected”. It was noted that there were insufficient filters to prevent such behavior, particularly on platforms like Mil

Anuncios, where the women interviewed found some advertisements with inappropriate content.

The following table summarizes the main online barriers that were mentioned during the focus groups:

Table 7. List of online challenges faced by migrant women to search for employment opportunities

Themes	Description
Lack of digital skills to enter information.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of skills to use digital tools, making it difficult to create an online resume (CV). Need to acquire basic knowledge, especially in terms of online privacy and security. - Digital literacy issues for using platforms or analyzing more data in job searches.
Lack of trust in digital environment and digital connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Problems with digital connectivity were reported, including lack of coverage, slow servers for data entry, and difficulty accessing various platforms. - Although there is large Internet free coverage, speed is low.
Infrastructure Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They use mobiles, and less laptop or desktop computers. This limits use of certain applications or resources. - In many cases, interviewees mentioned that they either didn't have access to a computer upon arriving in the country or couldn't use one, leading to the majority of job searches being done on mobile devices, which limits certain applications and resources.
Gender and Intersectional Bias	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Keyword issues that can hinder the search or selection of specific profiles and exclusion of their CVs based on gender or other variables.
Regional languages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People have concerns that they might be excluded when applying for these jobs on online platforms, as soon as they click on the "No" tick on the languages box.
Regulatory aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fear of lacking legal documentation. Some interviewees refrain from using online platforms due to concerns about potential legal issues. - Many interviewees expressed concerns about being identified on online platforms if they don't have legal documentation in Spain (e.g., a residence or work permit). This issue limits their job opportunities and access to digital platforms like search engines.
Fear of being cheated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issues with scams and inappropriate messages. They receive a lot of advertising, messages, and contacts that can pose a risk of phishing.

Request for data considered excessive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Warning about the importance of being cautious when sharing information online, including blindly accepting privacy policies and website and app terms and conditions. - Challenges with respect to privacy on job platforms, such as InfoJobs, where notifications and ads may be sent to personal email and should be managed properly.
Digital distrust to platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of specific recommendations and references when dealing with unknown individuals online, which doesn't instill much confidence in some platforms.
Workplace harassment and Online harassment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In several cases, it manifested as sexual harassment after contacting people through job search platforms. The women interviewed said that they went to work and met men who asked them for sexual actions or touched them, etc. As well as abuse of power, they were not paid or took advantage of the situation of vulnerability and phone harassment after publishing their personal data on these platforms. Many times, they stop using these means due to fears of encountering perverse profiles again. Anonymity and the lack of adequate channels for reporting are seen as a serious problem for users. - They experienced job vulnerability due to the lack of stability and protection against harassment on online job platforms. There weren't enough filters to prevent this type of behavior on platforms like Mil Anuncios where they found unsuitable job offers.

4.4. Challenges in job search participation

It is important for the connection and participation of citizens in the developments to not fall into the “vision trap” of technicians who ignore the problems and suffering in our research of migrant women. The interviews stated that many, since they do not have the information they request such as national identification DNI (national ID) or Diploma documentation are automatically excluded from these search platforms. The challenges associated with the homologation of diplomas can also act as significant barriers, as the process is lengthy and complex, often not recognizing qualifications from non-EU third countries. Therefore, providing insight into these private sector blind spots in technology development for the selection and recruitment process could innovatively and proactively improve practices for creating and using trusted technology.

The concept of algorithmic justice aims to ensure that all individuals are treated fairly and without prejudice, regardless of their demographic characteristics and their intersectionality that generates new discriminations such as race, gender, origin and other protected attributes. Datasets could be made more representative, and algorithms could be designed to avoid errors, noise, overfitting, or underfitting. The survey conducted supports this perception of discrimination, revealing that 54.4% of the respondents, including both 'yes' and 'maybe' responses, encountered difficulties related to their age, gender, nationality, and the

intersection of these aspects in Spain, due to cultural and normative disparities. Furthermore, 80.9% of respondents conveyed their perception that the platforms are not appropriately designed to mitigate biases and discrimination in the selection process. Focus groups also reported experiencing challenging situations of discrimination.

Figure 7: Question 25. Perceptions over discriminatory practice

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

Figure 8: Question 22. Platforms designed to prevent bias or discrimination

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

Multiple causes of discrimination and its impact on psychological and self-confidence levels were revealed. It is essential to establish a reporting channel that allows individuals to denounce discrimination, harassment, or other unethical practices that may be occurring on job platforms. Additionally, a mechanism should be provided for clients and users to provide feedback to companies. This will enable open and direct communication between the parties involved. The following table summarizes the challenges and main problems suffered that were mentioned by women migrants:

Table 8. List of main problems suffered by migrant women

Themes	Description
Information on national documentation	- Some platforms require uploading national ID or residence documentation. Some people do not yet have this documentation in Spain to work legally.

Homologation of diplomas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulties in securing desired jobs due to the lack of equivalencies or recognition of foreign qualifications. - Lengthy time for diplomas to be recognized by Spain's Ministry of Education from a non-EU third country. Even for those people with undergraduate degrees (university), the Bachillerato is not recognized, and this should be convenient as it is the minimum requirement for some jobs. - Taxonomy categorization differs from one country to another. Example: in LATAM, Ana (name changed for anonymity) studied International Relations as a Bachelor's Degree, but in Spain it works at postgraduate level. It depends on the university degree: it is not the same to study Law (which you need double homologation), than an "easier" degree.
Self-image Self-confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They label themselves as migrants in a foreign country, and they only look for low-qualified jobs.
Masked discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linguistic discrimination and also discrimination based on accent. - Discrimination based on digital skills and lack of technical knowledge. - Discrimination against pregnant women in the workplace. - Discrimination based on ethnic origin and nationality. - Discrimination based on gender, age, and intersectionality with other factors nationality, ethnic origin, etc. - Discrimination and abuse due to vulnerability in legal status.
Lengthy time for diplomas to be recognized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greater employment opportunities and fair wages for individuals with recognized qualifications and regularized immigration status. Limited employment prospects and payments based on the agreement for undocumented or individuals without recognized qualifications.

4.5. A real life example: A migrant's quest for employment using digital technologies

Based on the focus groups and interviews with migrants, the research team was able to put together an example based on real life experiences on how migrants face difficulties such that might end up causing underperformance of certain machine-learning based models deployed in the field of hiring. Below, the story that depicts this journey of disadvantage caused by structural aspects that continue to reinforce the vulnerabilities of migrant women.

Please note that all names in this report have been changed to protect the anonymity of our sources.

Case 1 - A woman working in the care sector

Sara's decision to leave her home country was a complex combination of economic motivations, social challenges, and personal aspirations. Drawn by the promise of opportunities in a new place, she moved to Spain where she has a handful of acquaintances and a minimal support network. As she embarked on her job search, Sara encountered the difficulties of the process magnified by the frustration of using automated systems and the perception of algorithmic discrimination. Her academic qualifications and professional experience from her home country, though substantial, became of little value. The need to validate her titles without the necessary documentation proved to be an insurmountable challenge.

Facing financial difficulties, Sara immersed herself in building a local network, connecting with other women sharing similar experiences through WhatsApp groups and local NGOs. Simultaneously, she explored online job opportunities, only to encounter rigid requirements and a lack of responses and feedback from employers. The time-consuming application process hindered her progress, preventing her from even reaching the initial stages of algorithmic evaluation. Invisible to the algorithms due to her inability to apply, Sara redirected her efforts to the care and domestic service sector, as she mentioned *"you just don't think about working anymore in your sector and you forget about it, you have to work in what's available"*. Despite using mobile and sector-specific apps to find employment, she faced rejection based on questionable reasons, suspecting that her appearance or origin played a role. Determined to improve her personal and financial situation, Sara jumped to social media, using platforms like WhatsApp and Facebook to seek referrals for economic opportunities and advertise her services, where other kinds of algorithms are used in market places to show her results among millions of others. This approach gained traction, leading to multiple clients and the establishment of her own small business, selling handmade crafts and other products online. She is content that these platforms, though seemingly less professional or complex than corporate applicant tracking systems (ATS), do seem to work better because her services are directly advertised to a broader market of clients looking to pay for services or products like the ones she provides.

Years passed, and while Sara is doing better on her own, a desire to return to her professional field persisted. The pursuit of educational opportunities became her new goal, but financial barriers, including difficulties securing a scholarship, seem similar to those she faced when initially moving. Still, Sara remained determined to restart her studies. Her resilience has allowed her to take major steps in improving her condition, but at the cost of remaining at the periphery of the fast moving world of professional opportunities, which has been permeated by the use of technologies that perform better with large loads of data that she is unable to provide as a user. She remains positive that after her studies her skills and qualifications would be recognized and valued by a future employer.

Case 2 - A woman working at the intersection of technology and public policy

In the heart of Barcelona, Maria is a passionate professional working at the intersection of public policy and technology, and after arriving in Spain more than ten years ago, she found herself navigating the complexities of the job market. After studying and working in Latin America Maria traveled to Spain to continue her professional studies and started working in fields at the crossroads of innovation, communication, and human resources within both startups and public administration. Her current role involves working at a European level to empower citizens through data-informed public policy.

However, Maria's journey in the job market was far from straightforward. When she first arrived in Catalonia, the language barrier posed a significant challenge. Being a foreigner, she quickly discovered that not being proficient in the local language became a barrier to numerous job opportunities. Despite her ability to perform well in many positions, the language requirement proved difficult to sort out. In her quest for employment, Maria turned to job search platforms, hoping they would help bridge the gap. Unfortunately, her experience was not properly valued. The platforms seemed impersonal and ineffective, with rejection becoming a common theme. She used a job search platform only once and decided never to return. At that time, these platforms were seemingly manual, lacking the sophistication of AI or machine learning.

Maria has the opinion that the key to success in her sector lies in building a network of professionals. She argues that the current online job search platforms and Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS) are ill-suited for individuals like her with diverse expertise. These platforms, according to Maria, might work well for technical or routine professions where skills are straight forward— she said: “either you know a coding language or you don't, you have marketing experience or you don't”. While Maria acknowledges that she hasn't personally interacted with more sophisticated ATS, her friends in the sector applying to positions in big tech companies describe a lengthy and often frustrating process. She believes that these systems are “*not for her*”, as she mentioned in her own words, designed for professions with clear-cut requirements, leaving little room for those with “hybrid experiences” that may seem unusual but prove highly valuable when assessed by a human reviewer.

Maria's story shows the challenges faced by individuals with diverse and hybrid skill sets in the current algorithmic landscape of job recruitment, as there is little data that algorithms can ingest about their value for companies. As we explore issues of algorithmic discrimination in hiring, it is imperative to consider the limitations of existing systems and advocate for solutions that accommodate the richness of experiences like Maria's.

Section 5: Results and Discussion

In this section, based on the research questions posed in the methodology section, the report discusses the key findings from the field work about algorithmic discrimination in the context of employment opportunities for Latin American migrants in Spain. Employing a sociotechnical approach, the research analyzed the dynamics between users and digital systems deployed in the hiring process, expanding on the perceptions of discrimination in the hiring process embedded within machine learning algorithms. The report employed a mixed-methods research methodology including surveys, interviews, and focus groups, engaging with three main groups of actors: migrants from Latin America, predominantly women; developers; and recruiters. From the lens of critical theory and intersectionality, the research examined how the overlap of various demographic characteristics reveals the extent of disadvantage and discrimination faced by specific groups, notably migrant women aged between 30 and 60. While our consultation did include men, the predominant participation of women highlighted the specific challenges this group faces during the migration process. A notable observation was the tendency to perceive migration as a determinant of one's career trajectory, often affecting the overall experience of usage of digital platforms.

Participants in the consultation process primarily work in the care and domestic services sector, sharing their particular journey and experience in job search and advertisement, which does not fully match with a complete hiring process of a company, but rather they are mostly excluded even from starting this process. While some of the participants inadvertently utilized machine learning algorithms when promoting their services through social media, their formal interaction with such technologies in corporate hiring processes remains limited. This presents a significant challenge for developers and recruiters, as the scarcity of data on this group limits algorithmic performance, overall contributing to a less diverse workforce.

In this section, the report shares some of the insights obtained through the consultation process, focusing on the challenges faced by Latin American migrants in the Spanish job market, and the implications for algorithmic discrimination in the hiring process. Lastly, the report acknowledges the inherent limitations of the research methodology.

5.1 Research question 1: At what stages of the hiring process are algorithmic fairness and non-discrimination perceived to be at odds by migrants from Latin American origin seeking employment in Spain?

The landscape of machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms in the hiring process seems to be at an early phase, in particular from the perspective of engagement with migrants in Spain. The results of the field work conducted for this report reveals that there is limited awareness among both job seekers and employers regarding the fair and non-discriminatory use of these technologies. While migrants mostly use job search platforms and social media tools for job searches, with 91% relying on such systems, the challenges faced by consulted companies, like startups, scale-ups and an industry association in Spain, show an industry in

constant evolution. More mature technologies like the use of machine learning algorithms for ranking, profiling and matching face difficulties in effectively addressing and performing adequately with specific groups, especially those in vulnerable conditions, due to the scarcity of data and understanding of their unique behaviors and experiences.

Sophisticated machine-learning systems for sentiment analysis, job prediction, and alternative ranking methods are still in the experimental phase, affected by the absence of comprehensive data sets. Developers and companies emphasize the need for more representative and niche data to refine AI applications, ensuring they are both effective and non-discriminatory. However, the elusive nature of the concept of “algorithmic fairness” further complicates the operationalization of such concept, which is perceived to be a major obstacle in the development of trustworthy technologies.

Moreover, the current market dynamics reveal a preference for larger companies handling high application volumes, with smaller enterprises facing challenges in implementing machine learning in their hiring processes. From the perspective of surveyed participants, interaction with machine learning remains limited, with over 50% unsure of their engagement with these systems during job searches or at different stages of their employment search journey. This uncertainty shows the need for enhanced transparency as these technologies undergo rapid integration into hiring practices. During the focus groups, participants felt overwhelmed by the rapid incorporation of many different types of technologies that they can barely understand, and less so use to their benefit. In this sense, technical advancements in the field are met with varying levels of knowledge and engagement among migrants depending on education level, professional sector, and age given generational gaps, signaling that the use of AI/ML might be in the early phases of adoption in the hiring process. This panorama calls for further developments on AI fairness, increased transparency and explainability, and the accumulation of diverse and inclusive data to reduce inequality gaps and enhance the effectiveness of these technologies, particularly in the context of a diverse and dynamic group like migrants in Spain.

5.2 Research question 2: How do intersecting characteristics of origin, gender, race, education, and socioeconomic standing, interact and create unique forms of algorithmic interaction?

Challenges that migrants face to engage with hiring systems using machine learning algorithms

In particular, for migrant women from Latin America seeking employment opportunities, accessing systems that employ machine-learning algorithms in the hiring process presents a considerable barrier. This group of people encounters difficulties in establishing an entry point into platforms that use algorithms for ranking profiles, assessing skills, evaluating interview responses, and predicting job performance. Instead, the predominant interaction of these women is with generic job search engines and social media, reflecting a fragmented landscape of solutions, each demanding time-consuming applications. Professional platforms, despite

their potential, are underutilized by this demographic, with profiles often lacking the elements necessary to stand out.

While survey respondents demonstrate high educational achievements, 87% holding university and postgraduate degrees, the act of migration compels many to reorient their professional trajectories, adapting to non-professional settings. Notably, 75% of surveyed women, the majority in focus groups, express the need to work within the available opportunities, predominantly found in care and domestic services in Spain. The nature of migration, as highlighted in focus group discussions, becomes a defining factor in future success. Those migrating for academic purposes like obtaining a graduate or postgraduate degree in Spain, with solid economic foundations, or already having employment prospects have markedly better experiences compared to those facing harsh conditions or irregular migration motivated by economic constraints.

The inability of this population to access algorithmic hiring systems has profound implications for the data required by these systems. During focus groups, developers acknowledge the challenge of collecting diverse data, citing the current high cost for companies to obtain such data in the middle of high market competition and the difficulties to create communities of people beyond mainstream experience. Building and maintaining a community of diverse candidates is acknowledged as a critical yet challenging endeavor for algorithms to perform optimally and avoid the inadvertent exclusion of these migrant populations. As a result, Latin American migrant women find themselves outside the scope of these systems, further perpetuating barriers to their inclusion in the professional landscape.

“Not designed for me” kind-of technologies

Latin American migrants seeking employment in Spain experience a sentiment of exclusion from mainstream employment platforms. Both individuals in highly professional settings, working at the intersection of social sciences and technology, and those in less professional roles within the care and domestic service sector share the feeling that these platforms are simply "not for them." The survey conducted by this report backs this perception, revealing that 77% of respondents encounter difficulties aligning their experiences and skills with the labor expectations in Spain, owing to cultural and normative disparities, as shown in figure 9. Focus groups show the struggle to harmonize academic backgrounds, professional experiences, and skills with the specific requirements detailed in job postings. Frustrated candidates sometimes feel they need to resort to "tricking the system" by modifying their CVs to comply with rigid platform requirements by altering their professional experience, adding or removing keywords, as well as modifying years of experience. For example, one participant stated that she "felt uncomfortable filling out boxes of information on my nationality and my personal address because, at that time, I did not have an official, legal status in Spain". This practice highlights the platforms' failure to embrace true diversity and accommodate varied experiences that would in turn create significant value to recruiters and employers.

Figure 9: Question 17. Main Barriers

Source: Survey conducted as part of this research.

During the discussions in the focus group with developers and recruiters, it became clear that companies prioritize securing the right candidates but often lack the knowledge on how to integrate a diversity approach from the outset, particularly in the critical phase of posting a job opportunity. This knowledge gap perpetuates the perception that these systems are not tailored to the experiences of Latin American migrants. In this sense, 82% of participants express the belief that these platforms fail to foster equal opportunities for applicants, irrespective of origin or migratory status. An even higher percentage, 86%, feel that these platforms inadequately provide opportunities for minorities. In focus groups and interviews, participants shared a feeling of disadvantage, referring to a lack of resources and networks to support them when competing for job positions. Networks, which were deemed critical for job finding by 86% of respondents, are perceived as essential in both professional and non-professional settings.

This collective sentiment echoes a widespread belief that what truly facilitates job placement is a robust network of contacts, a resource often hard to obtain for migrants. The main feeling, shared by 86% of respondents, is that these platforms and systems are not designed to mitigate bias and discrimination in the selection process. As a result, Latin American migrants in Spain feel that these platforms are not designed for them, thus being used a couple of times before permanently avoiding their usage for job search.

5.3 Research question 3: *How innovative strategies, visions and narratives could be harnessed to promote the development of robust, inclusive and trustworthy online platforms for hiring?*

The driving visions and market opportunity to deploy machine learning algorithms into the hiring process: the perspective of businesses in Spain

From a developer's standpoint based on the discussion of the focus group with private sector entities, the integration of machine learning algorithms into the hiring process represents a promising market opportunity, driven by the need of companies and recruiters for speed and efficiency in talent selection. The primary value proposition lies in expediting the identification of top talent while minimizing friction in the hiring journey. Companies are concerned about selecting the wrong candidates and often view interviews as cumbersome, so they seek for streamlined processes that provide comprehensive insights and good inputs for decision-making. Developers are aware of the need to enhance candidate experiences and ensure that employers derive value from the recruitment of high-caliber individuals. Beyond these considerations, developers are making efforts to assist their clients in meeting diversity goals, acknowledging the challenge of finding people at scale while striking a balance between individual complexities and the broader classification of groups.

In this sense, developers perceive they can obtain and provide substantial market value in reshaping their roadmaps to show tangible improvements in fairness and bias mitigation. The focus extends beyond mere algorithmic efficiency to the development of robust, sustainable, and trustworthy solutions. This commitment to efficiency and ethical considerations shows developers' concern to address the complexities of the hiring landscape. By aligning their goals with the broader objectives of enhancing fairness, mitigating bias, and contributing to diverse and inclusive hiring practices, developers aim to create a lasting impact in the field, meeting the evolving needs of companies while ensuring ethical and responsible deployment of machine learning algorithms in the hiring domain, even though they also recognize this is a work in progress.

Developing machine-learning models consistent with fairness and non-discrimination: initial steps

In response to the growing awareness of fairness and transparency concerns associated with machine learning-based hiring systems, the developers consulted in the focus group shared how they are actively engaged in efforts to design models consistent with fairness. These businesses recognize the potential biases inherent in their data collection processes, so companies are taking deliberate steps to address these issues and transform them into opportunities to enhance the overall value of their products. To achieve this, they are adopting a more substantive approach in terms of fairness, bias and transparency, moving beyond merely tackling issues to creating value from them. Developers acknowledge the limitations of data collection capabilities, emphasizing the need to avoid overcomplexity and overfeeding the system with data whose generalizability into future situations remains uncertain. So feature engineering here plays a key role in establishing adequate metrics for evaluation, profiling, categorizing and matching.

Furthermore, developers shared how they are incorporating more constant conversations within their companies about demographic and personal characteristics in algorithms and systems. This involves assessing the degree of "contamination" in terms of fairness or biases and implementing measures to mitigate them. Rather than solely focusing on individual

predictions, companies are striving to recognize the human value in the assessments of who should join their platforms to enrich their diversity and thus have an impact on the data they generate. These experimental initiatives involve parsing interview conversations and leveraging other tools to predict project outcomes and assess factors like communication and other soft skills.

These are some examples that show how developers aim to address systemic biases and challenges within the hiring process. By conducting rigorous evaluations, engaging in transparent discussions, and incorporating a range of signals beyond conventional markers of good candidates, these developers hope to actively contribute to the evolution of machine learning models that prioritize fairness, transparency, and overall effectiveness in talent selection.

Looking inside the black box?

In the field of algorithmic hiring, transparency emerges as a pressing concern. Among respondents of the survey for migrants, more than 41% believe they've engaged with machine-learning or artificial intelligence-based platforms, while a significant 50% remain uncertain about their interactions with such systems. The fact that the interaction with automated systems in hiring remains largely unknown to applicants is relevant to the extent that there is little knowledge on how to leverage such technologies from the perspective of candidates. During the focus groups discussions with migrants the need to know basic aspects of the technologies being used became apparent. Participants mentioned that the fast-paced digital transformation that followed the global pandemic of COVID-19 had a negative impact on people still trying to process the degree of change and adapt to the new digital landscape and harness its full potential. In this sense, participants considered that transparency regarding the evaluation process and feedback mechanisms is deemed indispensable from the time these systems are commercially released.

This concern extends beyond users to developers dealing with the inherent opaqueness of algorithms and AI systems. According to participants in the focus group with the private sector, even the most proficient engineers encounter challenges in understanding these complex systems, raising questions about accountability and decision-making processes. The developers expressed a shared concern about ensuring openness, allowing external influences to shape the development of tools. In this sense, companies recognize the opportunities ahead in terms of transparency, but it remains unclear what standards will prevail according to the systems, sectors and technologies used.

In sum, transparency is closely linked to the perceived usefulness and trustworthiness of algorithmic hiring solutions. The less transparent these systems, the less appealing they become for individuals already dealing with substantial challenges.

What about collecting more data about migrants for algorithms to perform better?

The question of whether more data is desirable for feeding machine learning-based systems in the context of fairness and non-discrimination in hiring is an open question. Based on the focus group with private companies, it was recognized that while more data may improve the performance of these systems, it might not necessarily be the only strategy required to address the broader challenges associated with discrimination in hiring processes. The key consideration is whether the focus should be solely on quantifiable data or if alternative approaches that prioritize addressing offline aspects first would be more effective.

After consultations with companies and migrants, it seems that without addressing offline issues, such as structural impediments and challenges faced by marginalized groups in professional activities, technological solutions are unlikely to yield significant improvements. Therefore, there is a need for a simultaneous strategy of inclusion that tackles both the technological aspects and the underlying offline problems.

Additionally, one of the problems is how to generate more data. One of the alternatives employed by private companies is to create their own communities to generate their own data in their platforms. However, the issue of inclusive participation emerges as a challenge for fragmented and atomized communities like that of migrants, who often have little time to engage beyond their immediate work responsibilities.

It remains an open question to see whether the issue of inclusivity could be solely addressed by a data generation strategy to enhance the performance of algorithms with certain populations, and ensure equitable outcomes in the hiring process.

Research limitations

This expert report delved into algorithmic discrimination in hiring using a mixed methods methodology, employing field research techniques such as three focus groups, a survey, and one-to-one interviews. The decision to utilize mixed methods stemmed from the study's primary goal of exploring perceptions rather than striving for quantitative representativeness in understanding the unique journey migrants undertake in their engagement with digital technologies for job searches. This is why it is important to acknowledge the study's limitations.

The non-representative nature of the sample, combined with scope constraints hindered larger-scale consultations and the creation of statistically significant samples. This might set the basis for a national and more representative consultation to analyze the dynamics of different sub groups of people in Spain. The fieldwork was predominantly concentrated in major cities like Bilbao, Barcelona, and Madrid, potentially limiting the broader national and inclusive perspective of the study. Moreover, the participant pool skewed towards women working in non-professional settings, pointing to a gap in the research's coverage of more professional sectors within the Spanish economy. Furthermore, a larger sample size in the analysis could be very conducive to a more comprehensive understanding of the overall picture. The study acknowledges these limitations, emphasizing the need for further research

to provide a more comprehensive understanding of algorithmic discrimination in hiring, particularly in diverse professional contexts and across varied geographic regions that might show nuances and particularities of different geographies where barriers such as “language”, might not be as present as in the Basque Country or Catalonia, the autonomous communities where focus groups were conducted.

Section 6: Recommendations

This project has provided a multifaceted assessment on whether and how algorithmic discrimination takes place in the hiring process, through the case study of Latin American migrant women in Spain. To this end, this project has evaluated the level of knowledge, situational awareness, capacities, and perceptions from three target groups: developers, job seekers and companies.

This chapter aims to be a tool for policy guidance on how this issue should be addressed. To this end, it is divided in three sets of recommendations: overall policy recommendations for the identified issue; thematic recommendations for each of the sub-set of issue-based challenges; and recommendations for each of target groups, both individually and in their mutual relationship.

6.1 Policy Recommendations

Embed algorithmic discrimination as an element of broader policy discussion in the public sector at three levels: labor law, immigration policy initiatives, and targeted measures on social exclusion. The analysis of algorithmic discrimination has grown in recent years from an academic and scholarly perspective. While still there is limited research-based data, civil society organizations have shown concerns over this issue. However, when it comes down to policy making, algorithmic discrimination has been limitedly included in the roadmaps, Action Plans and Operational Measures of the public administration. Except for related topics as platform workers and guidelines for algorithmic auditing in the selection process at the Ministry of Labour, algorithmic discrimination has not been addressed as a top-tier priority.

Create dedicated working groups on algorithmic discrimination in Spanish ICT-related industry associations. Industry associations do participate in workshops, discussion panels and public events where algorithmic discrimination is mentioned, either as an element among others or as an important topic. Some associations have made efforts to create certificates on AI transparency that focus on six significant domains to evaluate criteria: data sources, datasets, model building and selection, processing and minimization of harm, security measures and information access, and post-deployment monitoring of AI systems. This is the case of Adigital’s Algorithmic Transparency Certification for Artificial Intelligence Systems (2023) that has been accepted as part of the OECD repository. However, the majority of cases are working groups on Artificial Intelligence and data analytics that focus on economic growth, political affairs, and other societal goals such as how to leverage AI for territorial and social cohesion. Yet the discussions on how algorithms should be governed from a perspective of non-discrimination are limited.

Include workshops and discussion panels about the impact of algorithms on Human Resources processes in -annual conferences that national Spanish human resources associations host yearly. It is complex to identify the best strategy to inform each of the human resources teams across all sectors, industries, and company sizes in Spain, especially taking into account that more than 90% of Spanish companies are small- and medium-sized, and sometimes they rely on Temporary Employment Agencies, or “ETTs” as called in Spanish (companies that manage the contracts of temporary jobs between employees and employers) or even hire their own employees with no HR staff. Some human resources associations host yearly conferences in Spain to address the emerging trends and challenges that this group should identify as key elements to adapt their own internal processes to the social reality. **The main challenge in here is the fact that associations tend to be mostly composed of HR staff that belongs to the same sector** (e.g., consultancy, energy sector, business analytics, real estate), **and there is limited room for interaction and communication across sectors** (e.g., a HR staff working on an NGO on development cooperation with a HR staff from real estate industry).

Do not expect NGOs and CSOs to be the only responsible for addressing and creating awareness about the impact of algorithmic discrimination with their recipient members (Latin American migrant women in Spain). Instead, a social entity should be in charge of creating and coordinating a network of NGOs and CSOs that would receive these training. CSOs and NGOs working with Latin American migrant women tend to have limited financing and a small human workforce that is devoted only to the most pressing needs (social workers, psychologists, lawyers, social educators). In turn, they have highlighted that they need to carry out functions that go beyond their expertise, due to the lack of material resources. All organizations have shown interest in the topic, but do not have the resources to address it on their own. In order to make CSOs and NGOs be incentivized to participate in these activities, they should be invited to be part of them by a coordinating entity.

Include the impact of technology on migrants, particularly women, as part of National Institutes that have a legitimate, permanent presence, voice, and influence in meetings with Ministries. Concerns and demands from small, grassroots NGOs at the local level are usually channeled through “Mesas de Diálogo Social” (Social Dialogue Roundtables), hosted by National Institutes, which are the bridge with representatives from Ministries. For example, SEDOAC has belonged to the “Mesa Estatal de Cuidados” (National Roundtable on Care), which led to the release of a White Paper on care issues such as governance, informal economy, dependent people, family with only one mother, by the Institute for Women. Informed NGOs may move up their demands on algorithmic discriminations to these roundtables. However, this is not the most frequent case. This project has identified that they have limited knowledge about this issue, and the main focus is put onto the usage of digital devices (laptops, phones) and social media (Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter) to apply for jobs.

Assess offline barriers that Latin American migrant women face before applying for a job. This is an underexplored topic in the research over algorithmic discrimination in the hiring process. The lack of regularized documentation in Spain, the problems drawn from the limitations to get their university titles recognized in Spain, and the limited access to digital

infrastructure (most of the aged migrant women use phones and do not have laptops or Internet connectivity) are offline barriers that disincentivize women to search for jobs online.

Address the challenges of algorithmic discrimination differently depending on the age and generation of Latin American migrant women. Focus groups and interviews have engaged women from different age groups (mostly 20-30 and 45-65). Their realities were different, as younger women tend to have undergraduate (Bachelor's degree) and graduate degrees (Master's, PhDs) and, with some exceptions, they are facing problems to find a job on their topic. They identify the discrimination to happen when they are asked to include their graduation title, as it is not recognized in Spain. In some cases, their application has been automatically rejected a few minutes later because of the lack of this title, which underscores the existence of an algorithm behind the hiring process on certain websites. Women from 45 to 65 years old do not face these issues because they tend to apply for jobs offsite.

Particularly in young migrant women, train them to have digital literacy and learn strategies to overcome these discriminations.

Address the impact of online job search on sexual harassment. It is essential to establish a reporting channel that allows individuals to denounce discrimination, harassment, or other unethical practices that may be occurring on job platforms. Additionally, a mechanism should be provided for clients and users to provide feedback to companies. This will enable open and direct communication between the parties involved.

6.2 Target groups

6.2.1 Developers

Understand that the usage of algorithms for job selection in Latin American migrant women cannot be framed similarly to hiring processes for massive employee recruitment in large companies. Some interviewed companies uptake AI for companies that tend to have a high rate of hires and dropouts monthly. However, migrant women tend to search for jobs in small-sized companies, households or tend to apply for jobs through "ETTs".

Avoid preliminary discriminations in the early stage of job posting. Do not only rely on AI-generated content for job descriptions to understand the company's own recruitment needs. In the focus group with companies, a specific point was raised on how some companies use AI to generate the content of the job description. This means that the exclusion of certain socio-demographic groups may happen from the very "job posting" stage, and not necessarily at the time of the candidate's application.

Incentivize applicants to understand their views and concerns over the usage of algorithms after the interview process has taken place. When AI is used to select candidates, they receive a survey. However, there are no incentives for them to write down their concerns (because they do not have the time to do so, because they have negative emotions over the selection process). Some companies in focus groups fine-tune models using feedback from users and employees to foster a two-sided matching to account for interactions between

preferences and opportunities. While this model is feasible in companies that are focused on gathering data from both sides (employers and potential employees), some organizations do not have access to this valuable data. They should incentivize candidates to write down their suggestions to improve their own system.

Assess the implications of algorithmic systems across all stages, and not only in the business' portfolio. Most participants in this project did not have any significant expertise in this issue beyond the first stage (job postings). There was limited knowledge in other stages such as profiling, ranking, candidates shortlisting, and performance predicting.

In the "ranking and profiling" stage, consider the differences in vocabulary and ways of expressing themselves from candidates when writing cover letters. Some companies in focus groups acknowledged the usage of sentiment analysis to parse the cover letters to find specific emotions. However, there is a need to understand that people from different origins (even if using the same language, Spanish) may have different ways of expressing themselves, and this may lead to discrimination if emotions are not identified as those expected.

In the "predicting" stage, embed the user experience and digital literacy as "compensatory elements" to reduce potential discriminations. For instance, a company working on algorithmic usage for initiatives with refugees reflected on how they have tried to be mindful of what people will answer in their job applications, and of the limited time given struggles with employment. They have also partnered with development cooperation agencies and international organizations to understand which elements they should include to compensate for the discriminations that the algorithm may automatically trigger.

In the "recruitment" stage, provide shortlisted candidates with guidance on how they may leverage most of the interview. For example, some companies said that they want shortlisted candidates to be highly specific on their previous experiences. They also acknowledged that certain groups, such as migrant women, may not be used to providing these specific experiences as they have not received training to do so.

Collect more representative and niche data. Data provenance is key to ensure that the usage of algorithmic systems is fair. There is a two-fold need. First, ensure that companies collect more diverse, representative data from all types of groups. Second, search for niche data to understand how certain groups may have differences during the job search (for example, when writing different keywords, different wordings they are not used to putting into practice). A clear example was how the focus group raised the idea that there were "non-obvious candidates".

Collaborate with other departments in your companies focused on compliance and cybersecurity. Data security and privacy is a key element for employees' rights. This also applies to the algorithmic usage of data to process information and provide recommendations and solutions. European Union's laws are increasingly connecting cybersecurity laws with AI-related initiatives and regulations. Organizations such as the OAS, UN Women, UNESCO and other international entities are placing a key focus on cybersecurity with a gender

perspective. Therefore, it is essential to incorporate recommendations and training to prioritize the protection of women users.

Conduct red teaming exercises to test the algorithm. Red teaming exercises have been frequent in cybersecurity scenarios. However, increasingly big tech companies are applying AI red team exercises. This should be a tool to be extended across all types of companies handling AI. Particularly, the United Kingdom's Safety AI Summit has conducted briefing panels on the need to make use of red teamings for AI. To give an example, the AI Red Team should focus on attacks on AI systems, such as prompt attacks, extraction of training data, backdooring the AI model, adversarial examples to trick the model, data poisoning, and exfiltration.

Embed algorithmic impact assessments and algorithmic auditing. This is particularly of interest vis-à-vis risk cases that the EU legislation is proposing for AI.

Educate and train on how to introduce the gender dimension in develop tools focusing on the social impact of AI and its applications for social good. Incorporate a socially inclusive and interdisciplinary perspective in shaping cross-cutting solutions in the field of human resources and artificial intelligence during the the design, development, and evaluation of technological tools to prevent bias and facilitate social participation.

6.2.2 Companies doing recruitment

Produce a top-down managerial strategy to consider how algorithmic discrimination may be created during the development process. Ensure this strategy is not only an element of a checklist to be completed. The strategy should include an inter-departmental operational plan with three points of contact in each department (human resources, developers, business strategy) to address twice per year how to adapt their portfolio of algorithmic services to non-discrimination approaches. **A set of incentives for developers to compute and reduce algorithmic discrimination is another option, although an incentives-based system is not the most recommendable alternative** as it may lead to an economic mindset where algorithmic discrimination is only addressed by developers due to bonus reasons (bonuses that may experience ups and downs over time depending on the company's financial situation).

Guarantee that personal information that is transmitted in online applications are duly protected under data privacy regulations and do not get stored in data spaces, particularly for women migrant in situations of vulnerability. As identified in interviews, when women are searching for jobs online, they usually tend to send many personal information that may be sensitive if unlawfully used, such as whom they live with, which personal address they do have, or their bank account number. This is flagged as a potential security threat, both for the discriminations that may be drawn in the algorithmic processing of data, and for their own security as migrants that, in some cases, may not have strong social ties on the ground. A commonality among most interviewees is the **fear for their personal data to be sold to other industries (insurance, police, homeland security) or to be leaked by unlawful actors (transnational crime networks, specific persons that aim to commit a harm towards certain person, e.g. previous background on gender-based violence).**

Collaboration with NGOs facilitates the establishment of connections with diverse profiles, while mitigating biases that may exist within companies. Diversifying the channels for talent acquisition is essential to ensure a broader range of skills and perspectives within our teams. This diversification can be accomplished through partnerships with NGOs specializing in women in science, women from Latin America, women migrants, and others. Such diversification will significantly enhance both efficiency and innovation within companies.

Committees for equity, equality, and diversity (EDI) working in collaboration with development teams and the HR staff are essential. It is important for companies to have specialized teams at a cultural level to guide actions, as well as to implement anti-harassment and discrimination protocols that ensure the well-being of users in line with legal standards.

6.2.3 Policymakers

Increase public funds, both at the national and regional levels, devoted to address algorithmic discrimination in recipient civil society organizations and NGOs in three layers: (1) situational awareness and training; (2) capacity-building actions; and (3) advocacy strategies. Ensure there is no incompatibility in receiving public funds from different units in the same public administration to address both the long-lasting topics and emerging topics that NGOs may aim to address. The project has identified that NGOs and civil society organizations (CSOs) in Spain have limited *knowledge, resources, and competences* to address algorithmic discrimination as part of their portfolio. The third point is particularly relevant, as some NGOs indicated that, even if they would aim to foster activities on this issue, they would not be able to do so because they are usually recipients of public funds from specific units and regional ministries to implement activities on the traditional topics they have long addressed. If they try to apply for new funds, from other units or regional ministries, for new topics such as algorithmic discrimination, they risk losing the funds for the original topics.

For instance, a Basque Country NGO indicated that they cannot do all the training they would like to do. They live on public funds from the Basque Public Administration, specifically from the area of Development Cooperation. Every time they leave their field of work and try to do new topics such as labor rights, the Department tells them that they cannot apply for Social Action, as these funds belong to social intervention NGOs and not to development cooperation NGOs, as they are. Their association is in charge of denunciation, advocacy. They cannot deal with training on labor rights for women workers.

Provide public officers with capacity building activities, such as training. Activate and increase trainings on algorithmic discrimination for public officers working in the public administration at the national level between the Secretary of State for Digitalization and Artificial Intelligence at the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation, and State Secretariats and General Directions at the Ministry of Labor, Ministry of Equality, Ministry of Migrations and Social Security. Also, **at the regional levels in each public administration.** Effective project management needs a highly skilled workforce first.

Foster technical assistance contracts between the public administration and individual consultants to support public administration's projects on algorithmic discrimination. Do not stick to briefing panels, public events, and outreach activities about the importance of this topic. Engage external expertise in the public administration to provide adapted impact assessments and practice-based use cases.

Address the discrimination to migrant women in hiring processes as part of the case scenarios that may be addressed in the new Spanish AI Sandbox Law that has entered into force in 2023. The Government of Spain, with the collaboration of the European Commission, launches the first controlled test environment to test how to implement the requirements applicable to high-risk Artificial Intelligence systems of the proposed European Regulation on Artificial Intelligence. The test environment enables cooperation between users and AI providers, and bring AI development companies closer to the competent authorities in order to provide clarity on the requirements to be set by the future AI Regulation for AI systems; facilitate the transfer of compliance know-how on the implementation of AI legislation; encourage innovation and promote the development of new reliable systems; test the obligations and requirements in a controlled environment and subsequently produce technical guides and the collection of the necessary information to be able to provide results on the whole project. These elements should include use cases on hiring processes for migrant women in Spain.

Adapt public procurement criteria to get funding. Consider including algorithmic auditing to ensure non-discrimination as part of the criteria to apply for and receive public funding in overall projects. Most funding projects in Spain are usually given on the basis of the cheapest offer in the public administration. However, innovative and structural reforms should take place under other criteria, such as diversity, transparency, explainability and traceability.

6.2.4 Social communities

Empower migrant women and engage them in order to interiorize measures on how they may fight against algorithmic discrimination. In a Focus Group, a woman indicated that she created a cooperative group with other Latin American migrants for socio-sanitary attention and cleaning activities. They published their services on Facebook and MilAnuncios. After some time, MilAnuncios offered them to pay a fee to position their cooperative on the first top positions on the website. They rejected this payment. However, this is an example of how Latin American migrant women may acquire the tools to know further about the challenges and opportunities -the feasibility, explainability, transparency and accountability- of algorithms when they offer their services online. This empowerment recommendation should be tackled through **training and workshops to be developed by social entities whose focus is on digital rights**. The landscape of digital rights NGOs in Spain is mostly concentrated in Barcelona, but it is growing in Valencia and Madrid.

Foster collaboration with other entities that may be complementary in the creation of a project on algorithmic discrimination. As some NGOs cannot receive certain types of funding, search for partners to build joint projects on this issue.

Consider making reference to the impact of algorithms in the community or NGOs Operational Plans and Work Plans. Although it is not a top priority and there are limited resources to address it, explicitly acknowledge the importance of this issue. Even if the organization does not trigger activities on this topic, the reference to this problematization may help add forces to potential advocacy activities vis-à-vis the public and private sectors.

Reduce the skepticism on the usage of online platforms to search for jobs, and suggest digital skills training packages to protect people's rights online. City Councils tend to do free training on digital skills. Collect information on the calendar dates of this external training, and inform your recipients about these opportunities.

References

- Acemoglu, Daron, and Simon Johnson. 2023. *Power and Progress: Our Thousand-Year Struggle Over Technology and Prosperity*. N.p.: Basic Books.
- Adler, Emmanuel, and Michael Faubert. 2022. "Epistemic Communities of Practice." In *Conceptualizing International Practices*, 47 - 76. UK: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009052504.003>.
- "Advancing accountability in AI: Governing and managing risks throughout the lifecycle for trustworthy AI." 2023. OECD iLibrary. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/science-and-technology/advancing-accountability-in-ai_2448fo4b-en.
- Antonsen, Trine, and Erik Lundestad. 2019. "Borgmann and the Non-Neutrality of Technology." *Techné: Research in Philosophy and Technology* 23 (1): 83-103. [10.5840/techne201951497](https://doi.org/10.5840/techne201951497).
- Aytekin, Ahmet B. 2023. "Algorithmic Bias in the Context of European Union Anti-Discrimination Directives." *CEUR-WS EWA'23: European Workshop on Algorithmic Fairness* 3442, no. 41 (June). <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3442/paper-41.pdf>.
- Celis, Elisa, Damian Satraszak, and Nisheeth K. Vishnoi. n.d. "Ranking with Fairness Constraints." 4. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1704.06840>.
- "Challenges for mitigating bias in algorithmic hiring | Brookings." 2019. Brookings Institution. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/challenges-for-mitigating-bias-in-algorithmic-hiring/>.
- Coaston, Jane. 2019. "Intersectionality, explained: meet Kimberlé Crenshaw, who coined the term." Vox. <https://www.vox.com/the-highlight/2019/5/20/18542843/intersectionality-conservatism-law-race-gender-discrimination>.
- Crenshaw, Kimberlé. 2019. *On Intersectionality: Essential Writings*. N.p.: New Press.
- Crenshaw, Kimberlé W. 1989. "Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics." *Columbia Law School*. https://scholarship.law.columbia.edu/faculty_scholarship/3007/.
- Davis, Laura M. 2023. "The New Age of Hiring: AI Is Changing the Game for Job Seekers." CNET. <https://www.cnet.com/tech/features/the-new-age-of-hiring-ai-is-changing-the-game-for-job-seekers/>.
- Davis, Michelle. 2023. "The New Age of Hiring: AI Is Changing the Game for Job Seekers." CNET. <https://www.cnet.com/tech/features/the-new-age-of-hiring-ai-is-changing-the-game-for-job-seekers/>.
- Digital Future Society. 2022. "La discriminación algorítmica en España: límites y potencial del marco legal." La discriminación algorítmica en España: límites y potencial del marco legal. <https://digitalfuturesociety.com/es/report/algorithmic-discrimination-in-spain/>.

- "Discriminación laboral en España: riesgos para las empresas." 2021. WTW Update.
<https://willistowerswatsonupdate.es/talento-y-retribucion/demandas-por-discriminacion-un-problema-incipiente/>.
- "Discrimination: your rights: How you can be discriminated against." n.d. GOV.UK. Accessed November 9, 2023.
<https://www.gov.uk/discrimination-your-rights/how-you-can-be-discriminated-against>.
- Dolata, Mateusz, Stefan Feuerriegel, and Gerhard Schwabe. 2021. "A Sociotechnical View of Algorithmic Fairness." *Information Systems Journal*, (September).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.09253>.
- Draude, Claude, Goda Klumbyte, Phillip Lüking, and Pat Treusch. 2020. "Situated algorithms: a sociotechnical systemic approach to bias." *Online Information Review* 4, no. 2 (June): 325-342. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-10-2018-0332>.
- España Digital Gobierno de España. 2023. "Informe sobre los avances en la Estrategia Nacional de Inteligencia Artificial." Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital.
https://portal.mineco.gob.es/RecursosNoticia/mineco/prensa/noticias/2023/20230522_informe_enia.pdf.
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2023. "Being Black in the EU – Experiences of people of African descent." (October). doi:10.2811/327480.
- Flynn, Jack. 2023. "15+ Essential Social Media Recruitment Statistics [2023]: How Effective Is Social Media Recruiting?" Zippia.
<https://www.zippia.com/advice/social-media-recruitment-statistics/>.
- "G7 Hiroshima Process on Generative Artificial Intelligence." 2023. OECD iLibrary.
<https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/bf3coc60-en.pdf?expires=1699373457&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=373552BBDC7D40BF6BE5F174DA27D04C>.
- Geyik, Sahin Cem, Stuart Ambler, and Krishnamurthy Kenthapadi. 2019. "Fairness-Aware Ranking in Search & Recommendation Systems with Application to LinkedIn Talent Search." *KDD '19: Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining*, (July), 2221-2231. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3292500.3330691>.
- Ghosh, Avijit, Ritam Dutt, and Christo Wilson. 2021. "When Fair Ranking Meets Uncertain Inference." *SIGIR 2021* 1033 (43). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3404835.3462850>.
- Ghosh, Avijit, Rittam Dutt, and Christo Wilson. 2021. "When Fair Ranking Meets Uncertain Inference." *SIGIR 2021 - Proceedings of the 44th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, 1033-1043.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3404835.3462850>.
- Gómez, Aitor, Carme Elboj, and Marta Capllonch. 2013. "Beyond Action Research: The Communicative Methodology of Research." *Qualitative Research* 6, no. 2 (August): 183-197. <https://doi.org/10.1525/irqr.2013.6.2.183>.
- GRIN. 2023. "Understanding the Creator Economy: A Complete Guide." Accessed November 8, 2023. <https://grin.co/blog/understanding-the-creator-economy/>.
- Hu, Lily. 2023. "What is "Race" in Algorithmic Discrimination on the Basis of Race?" *Journal of Moral Philosophy*, (September). <https://doi.org/10.1163/17455243-20234369>.
- Kassir, Sara, Lewis Baker, Jackson Dolphin, and Frida Polli. 2022. "AI for hiring in context: a perspective on overcoming the unique challenges of employment research to mitigate disparate impact." *AI and Ethics* 3 (September): 845–868.

- <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-022-00208-x>.
- Kleinberg, Jon, Sendhil Mullainathan, and Manish Raghavan. 2017. "Inherent Trade-Offs in the Fair Determination of Risk Scores." *Proceedings of Innovations in Theoretical Computer Science (ITCS)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1609.05807>.
- Köchling, Alina, and Marius C. Wehner. 2022. "Better explaining the benefits why AI? Analyzing the impact of explaining the benefits of AI-supported selection on applicant responses." (December). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijsa.12412>.
- Kolmar, Chris. 2023. "15+ Incredible Job Search Statistics [2023]: What Job Seekers Need To Know." Zippia. <https://www.zippia.com/advice/job-search-statistics/>.
- Liscomb, Megan. 2022. "Millennials Are Sharing Recession-Survival Tips For Gen Z, And We Really Learned This Stuff The Hard Way." BuzzFeed. <https://www.buzzfeed.com/meganeliscomb/millennial-recession-tips-gen-z>.
- Makarius, Erin E., Debmalya Mukherjee, Joseph D. Fox, and Alexa K. Fox. 2020. "Rising with the machines: A sociotechnical framework for bringing artificial intelligence into the organization." *Journal of Business Research* 120 (November): 262-273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.07.045>.
- McLaughlin, J.E., M. Wolcott, and D. Hubbard. 2019. "A qualitative review of the design thinking framework in health professions education - BMC Medical Education." *BMC Medical Education* 19, no. 98 (April). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1528-8>.
- Mercer. 2022. "Win with Empathy." Mercer. <https://www.mercer.com/Content/Dam/Mercer/Attachments/Private/Global-Talent-Trends-2020-Report.Pdf>.
- Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital de España. 2023. "Invisibilización y discriminación algorítmica." Invisibilización y discriminación algorítmica. <https://datos.gob.es/es/blog/invisibilizacion-y-discriminacion-algoritmica>.
- Morondo, Dolores, Josu A. Eguliz Castañeira, and Tanya Álvarez. 2022. "Algorithmic discrimination in Spain." Digital Future Society. <https://digitalfuturesociety.com/report/algorithmic-discrimination-in-spain/>.
- The New York City Council. 2021. "The New York City Council - File #: Int 1894-2020." The New York City Council - Calendar. <https://legistar.council.nyc.gov/LegislationDetail.aspx?ID=4344524&GUID=B051915D-A9AC-451E-81F8-6596032FA3F9&Options=ID%7CText%7C&Search=>.
- NYC: Consumer and Worker Protection. 2023. "Automated Employment Decision Tools: Frequently Asked Questions." NYC.gov. <https://www.nyc.gov/assets/dca/downloads/pdf/about/DCWP-AEDT-FAQ.pdf>.
- "OECD Catalogue of Tools and Metrics for Trustworthy AI." 2023. OECD.AI. <https://oecd.ai/en/catalogue/overview>
- "OECD Framework for the Classification of AI Systems." 2019. OECD iLibrary. <https://www.astrid-online.it/static/upload/cb6d/cb6dgeca-en.pdf>.
- Ovalle, Anaelia, Arjun Subramonian, Vagrant Gautman, Gilbert Gee, and Kai-Wei Chang. 2023. "Factoring the Matrix of Domination: A Critical Review and Reimagination of Intersectionality in AI Fairness." *AIES 2023*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.17555>.
- Pasquale, F. 2015. *The Black Box Society*. Harvard University Press.
- Peral, Sergio L., and Madelyn Geldenhuys. 2020. "The indirect relationship between

- personality and performance through job crafting behaviour." *SA Journal of Psychology* 46, no. a1715 (March). <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v46io.1715>.
- Queen's University. n.d. "Positionality Statement | Centre for Teaching and Learning." Accessed November 5, 2023. <https://www.queensu.ca/ctl/resources/equity-diversity-inclusivity/positionality-statement>.
- Raghavan, Manish, Solon Barocas, Jon Kleinberg, and Karen Levy. 2020. "Mitigating bias in algorithmic hiring: evaluating claims and practices." *FAT* '20: Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, (January), 469-481. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372828>.
- Raghavan, Manish, Manish Purohit, and Sreenivas Gollupadi. 2019. "Hiring Under Uncertainty." (May). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1905.02709>.
- Rose, Ellen. 2012. "Not "Just a Tool": A Triadic Model of Technological Non-Neutrality." *Educational Technology* 52, no. 1 (February): 17-21. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44429984>.
- Sartori, Laura, and Andreas Theodorou. 2022. "A sociotechnical perspective for the future of AI: narratives, inequalities, and human control." *Ethics and Information Technology* 24, no. 4 (January). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-022-09624-3>.
- Schroeder, Ralph. 2018. *Social Theory after the Internet: Media, Technology, and Globalization*. USA: UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt2okrxdr>.
- Schwartz, Reva, Apostol Vassilev, Kristen Greene, Lori Perine, Andrew Burt, and Parick Hall. 2022. "Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence." *NIST Special Publication 1270*, (March). <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1270>.
- "Select Issues: Assessing Adverse Impact in Software, Algorithms, and Artificial Intelligence Used in Employment Selection Procedures Under Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964." 2023. EEOC. <https://www.eeoc.gov/laws/guidance/select-issues-assessing-adverse-impact-software-algorithms-and-artificial>.
- Sharma, Gaurav. 2018. "Technological Determinism: Perspectives on Technology and Social Change." *Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 8, no. 3 (June). <https://www.oijrj.org/oijrj/may-june2018/17.pdf>.
- Simandan, Dragos. 2019. "Revisiting positionality and the thesis of situated knowledge." *Dialogues in Human Geography* 9, no. 2 (June). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043820619850013>.
- Smith, Merritt R., and Leo Marx, eds. 1994. *Does Technology Drive History? The Dilemma of Technological Determinism*. N.p.: MIT Press.
- Steup, Matthias, and Ram Neta. 2005. "Epistemology (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)." Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/epistemology/>.
- Tannenbaum, Cara, Robert P. Ellis, Friederike Eyssel, James Zou, and Londa Schiebinger. 2019. "Sex and gender analysis improves science and engineering." *Nature* 575:137-146. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-019-1657-6>.
- Takacs, David. 2003. "How Does Your Positionality Bias Your Epistemology?" *UC Hastings College of the Law*. https://repository.uclawsf.edu/faculty_scholarship/1264.
- Technavio. 2022. "AI Market in Recruitment Industry by Component and Geography - Forecast

- and Analysis 2022-2026." Technavio Report.
https://www.technavio.com/Report/Ai-Market-Industry-in-Recruitment-Industry-Analysis?Utm_source=prnewswire&utm_medium=pressrelease&utm_campaign=T50-DCS_wk45_2022_004_report&utm_content=IRTNTR73507.
- Teodorescu, Mike. n.d. "Protected Attributes and "Fairness through Unawareness" | Exploring Fairness in Machine Learning for International Development | Supplemental Resources | MIT OpenCourseWare." MIT OpenCourseWare. Accessed November 9, 2023.
<https://ocw.mit.edu/courses/res-ec-001-exploring-fairness-in-machine-learning-for-international-development-spring-2020/pages/module-three-framework/protected-attributes/>.
- U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission. 2023. "Select Issues: Assessing Adverse Impact in Software, Algorithms, and Artificial Intelligence Used in Employment Selection Procedures Under Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964." Equal Employment Opportunity Commission.
<https://www.eeoc.gov/laws/guidance/select-issues-assessing-adverse-impact-software-algorithms-and-artificial>.
- Wachter, Sandra, Brent Mittelstadt, and Chris Russell. 2020. "Why Fairness Cannot Be Automated: Bridging the Gap Between EU Non-Discrimination Law and AI." *Computer Law & Security Review*, (March). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3547922>.
- Wang, Xiaomeng, Yishi Zhang, and Ruilin Zhu. 2022. "A brief review on algorithmic fairness." *Management System Engineering* 1 (7). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44176-022-00006-z>.
- White House. 2022. "Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights | OSTP." The White House.
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/ai-bill-of-rights/>.
- White House. 2023. "Executive Order on Further Advancing Racial Equity and Support for Underserved Communities Through The Federal Government." The White House.
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2023/02/16/executive-order-on-further-advancing-racial-equity-and-support-for-underserved-communities-through-the-federal-government/>.
- White House. 2023. "FACT SHEET: President Biden Issues Executive Order on Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence." The White House.
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2023/10/30/fact-sheet-president-biden-issues-executive-order-on-safe-secure-and-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence/>.
- Wodecki, Ben. 2022. "NIST calls for socio-technical to challenge AI biases - NIST calls for socio-technical to challenge AI biases." AI Business.
<https://aibusiness.com/verticals/nist-calls-for-socio-technical-to-challenge-ai-biases>.
- Xenidis, Raphaële, and Linda Senden. 2020. "EU non-discrimination law in the era of artificial intelligence : mapping the challenges of algorithmic discrimination." In *General Principles of EU Law and the EU Digital Order*, edited by Ulf Bernitz, Xavier Groussot, Jaan Paju, and Sybe Alexander d. Vries, 151-182. N.p.: Wolters Kluwer.
<https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/65845>.

Annex

A1. [Survey](#) (Link to full results, questions and options)

1. País de origen en América Latina
2. Edad (indicar solo el número de años cumplidos, por ejemplo: 35)
3. Género
4. Tipo de residencia en España
5. Nivel máximo de estudios alcanzado (nomenclatura estándar en América Latina)
6. Años de experiencia laboral
7. Sector laboral
8. Situación profesional actual
9. Tiempo buscando empleo
10. Principal forma de búsqueda de empleo
11. ¿Has utilizado plataformas de reclutamiento en línea para alguna o varias de las siguientes del proceso?
12. En el caso de que hayas utilizado cualquier herramienta en línea para la búsqueda de empleo, ¿cómo calificarías tu experiencia de uso?
13. ¿Cómo calificarías la efectividad de esta herramienta para conseguir un trabajo?
14. Nivel de familiaridad en el uso de estas herramientas, ¿qué tan comfortable te sientes al utilizarlas?
15. Tiempo promedio que te lleva cargar tu información en estas plataformas
16. ¿Puedes compartir una breve reseña de cuál ha sido tu experiencia en el uso de estas herramientas?, ¿la has encontrado útil, compleja, familiar, ajena?, ¿has conseguido empleo con el uso de estas herramientas?
17. Principales barreras del uso de estas plataformas
18. Uso de datos personales
19. ¿Cree usted que se ha utilizado inteligencia artificial para ser seleccionada o descartada en un proceso de selección? Según la UE: La IA permite que los sistemas tecnológicos perciban su entorno, se relacionen con él, resuelvan problemas y actúen con un fin específico. La máquina recibe datos (ya preparados o recopilados a través de sus propios sensores, por ejemplo, una cámara), los procesa y responde a ellos.
20. ¿Cuáles crees que son los principales obstáculos a la transparencia y explicabilidad del proceso de selección
21. ¿Crees que las plataformas de empleo en línea promueven la igualdad de oportunidades para todos los solicitantes, independientemente de su origen o situación?

22. ¿Sientes seguridad de que las plataformas de empleo en línea están diseñadas para prevenir sesgos y discriminación en el proceso de selección?
23. ¿Crees que las plataformas deberían implementar capacitaciones y políticas específicas para los empleadores para prevenir la discriminación en el proceso de selección?
24. ¿Sientes que las plataformas de empleo en línea ofrecen suficientes oportunidades para grupos minoritarios?
25. ¿Has experimentado situaciones en las que has percibido una preferencia de un empleador sobre otra persona por tu origen o sexo?
26. ¿Has tenido dificultades para comprender y cumplir con los requisitos legales y de documentación exigidos por algún empleador?
27. ¿Has enfrentado dificultades para adaptar tu experiencia y habilidades a las expectativas laborales en España debido a diferencias culturales o normativas?
28. ¿Has notado que la falta de relaciones personales y contactos en la búsqueda de empleo en línea es una barrera, en comparación con las oportunidades que podrías encontrar a través de conexiones personales fuera de línea?
29. ¿Consideras que tienes acceso a recursos de apoyo suficiente para encontrar un empleo en España?
30. ¿Crees que algo hizo falta en esta encuesta para entender las barreras en línea y fuera de línea que tienen las personas de origen latinoamericano cuando buscan empleo en España?
31. ¿Qué te ha parecido esta encuesta?

A2. Focus Groups

A2.1 Focus group with companies (Online, October 25th, 2023)

Esta es una guía que contiene las preguntas a realizar durante los grupos focales con migrantes latinoamericanos buscando empleo en España en Bilbao y Barcelona.

Las preguntas específicas y la información obtenida a través de estos grupos focales debería contribuir a responder dos de las tres preguntas de investigación aprobadas por el equipo de FINDHR, las cuales se detallan más abajo.

De acuerdo con el equipo de FINDHR, lo interesante sería entender si sienten que sus equipos son diversos, si saben cuáles son las formas o dimensiones en las que ocurre la discriminación, cuáles creen que son sus puntos ciegos y en los que requieren mayor fortaleza y cómo establecer esos canales de comunicación.

Preguntas de Investigación

1. ¿En qué etapas del proceso de contratación la equidad algorítmica y la no discriminación son percibidas como reñidas por los inmigrantes de origen latinoamericano que buscan empleo en España?

- a. ¿Cuál es el panorama de la automatización y el uso de sistemas basados en IA en el proceso de contratación en España?
- b. ¿Qué tipo de sistemas basados en IA desarrollan y utilizan las empresas durante todo el proceso de contratación?
2. ¿Cómo se podrían aprovechar estrategias, visiones y narrativas innovadoras para promover el desarrollo de plataformas de contratación en línea sólidas, inclusivas y confiables?
 - a. ¿Cuáles son los principales impedimentos para que las empresas (desarrolladores y usuarios) identifiquen, prevengan, mitiguen o corrijan resultados injustos conocidos de los algoritmos en el proceso de contratación?
 - b. ¿Cuáles son las dinámicas clave detrás del ecosistema de innovación tecnológica que obstaculizan la incorporación de enfoques éticos en el desarrollo de sus productos y servicios?

Preguntas específicas

1. ¿Qué consideraciones éticas y legales tienes en cuenta al utilizar fuentes de datos para entrenar tus modelos de IA? ¿Cómo te aseguras de que los datos utilizados sean representativos y no contengan sesgos inherentes?
 - a. ¿Qué tan amplia y estructurada es su base de datos sobre empleados y candidatos?
 - i. ¿Incluyen información sobre número de contrataciones, evaluaciones de desempeño y demás métricas que permitan garantizar la precisión y fiabilidad del modelo de IA?
 - b. Si bien es posible comprar bases de datos anonimizadas con información de otras empresas, ¿conocen el contexto particular de cada empresa incorporada en la base de datos y sus candidatos?
2. ¿Qué consideraciones realizas en cuanto a la transparencia y explicabilidad de tus sistemas de IA? ¿Cómo garantizas que los procesos de toma de decisiones de tu sistema sean comprensibles y explicables para los usuarios y candidatos?
3. ¿Cómo defines la justicia en el contexto de tu tecnología de IA utilizada en la selección de personal? ¿Qué medidas tomas para asegurar que tus sistemas sean justos y equitativos para todos los candidatos, independientemente de su origen o características personales?
4. ¿Cuáles son los principales desafíos éticos y técnicos que enfrentas al desarrollar sistemas de IA para el reclutamiento y selección de personal?
 - a. Los modelos predictivos se basan en datos históricos, ¿cómo cambiar la composición de los equipos y aumentar la diversidad si se buscan atributos previamente identificados?
5. ¿Cuáles son las principales características que buscan en un candidato y por qué? ¿Con qué base teórica o legal?
 - a. ¿Qué tipo de métricas buscan para seleccionar buenos candidatos?
 - b. ¿Cuáles son los parámetros de comparación, contra los mejores talentos o todos los talentos?
 - c. ¿Observan las diferencias entre los mejores talentos y los peores?
6. ¿Cómo evalúas el impacto de tus sistemas de IA en los candidatos y en el proceso de selección en general? ¿Has realizado estudios sobre el impacto dispar de tu tecnología en diferentes grupos demográficos o sociales?
 - a. ¿Cómo se justifica, o es posible justificar, el valor predictivo de determinadas variables, como: tiempo de traslado, expresiones faciales, tests de personalidad, posts en redes sociales, etc?

7. ¿Qué medidas tomas para garantizar la privacidad y seguridad de los datos de los candidatos en tus sistemas de IA? ¿Cómo te aseguras de cumplir con las regulaciones de protección de datos y privacidad, como el RGPD o normativas aplicables?
 - a. ¿Utilizan información proveniente de las redes sociales de los candidatos y los sitios web que visitan?, ¿cuál en particular?
 - b. "¿Establecen una restricción temporal en la información que consultan en las redes sociales y sitios web de los candidatos, es decir, hasta qué punto en el pasado revisan la información, ya sea a partir de la solicitud o durante la vida de los candidatos?"
8. ¿Puedes describir la composición de tu equipo de desarrollo de IA en términos de diversidad, incluyendo género, etnia y antecedentes culturales? ¿Qué medidas has tomado para promover la diversidad en tu equipo?
9. ¿Cómo abordas y comprendes los conceptos relacionados con la discriminación al desarrollar sistemas de IA para el reclutamiento y selección de personal? ¿Qué estrategias implementas para mitigar el riesgo de sesgo y discriminación en tus modelos?
10. ¿Qué medidas has implementado para identificar y mitigar sesgos en tus algoritmos de selección de personal? ¿Has realizado auditorías de sesgo y equidad en tus sistemas? Si es así, ¿qué aprendiste de ellas y cómo las has utilizado para mejorar tu tecnología?
11. ¿Cómo planeas mantenerte al tanto de las últimas investigaciones y avances en ética de IA y tecnologías justas, y cómo integran ese conocimiento en el desarrollo continuo de tus sistemas?

A2.2 Focus groups with migrants (Barcelona and Bilbao, October 7th, 2023)

Esta es una guía que contiene las preguntas a realizar durante los grupos focales con migrantes latinoamericanos buscando empleo en España en Bilbao y Barcelona.

Las preguntas específicas y la información obtenida a través de estos grupos focales debería contribuir a responder dos de las tres preguntas de investigación aprobadas por el equipo de FINDHR, las cuales se detallan más abajo.

Preguntas de Investigación

1. ¿En qué etapas del proceso de contratación la equidad algorítmica y la no discriminación son percibidas como reñidas por los inmigrantes de origen latinoamericano que buscan empleo en España?
 - a. ¿Cuál es el panorama de la automatización y el uso de sistemas basados en IA en el proceso de contratación en España?
 - b. ¿Qué tipo de sistemas basados en IA desarrollan y utilizan las empresas durante todo el proceso de contratación?
2. ¿Cómo interactúan las características interseccionales de origen, género, raza, educación y posición socioeconómica y crean formas únicas de interacción algorítmica?
 - a. ¿Cuáles son los desafíos específicos (en línea y fuera de línea) que enfrentan estas categorías superpuestas al interactuar con plataformas en línea?
 - b. ¿Cuáles son las características clave del diseño de las plataformas de contratación en línea que se consideran más injustas para el grupo mencionado anteriormente?

Preguntas específicas

BLOQUE 2

4. ¿Sientes que tus antecedentes culturales o experiencia internacional han influido en tus experiencias en procesos de selección? ¿De qué manera?

5. ¿Has tenido la oportunidad de proporcionar retroalimentación o comentarios sobre tu experiencia con sistemas de IA utilizados en procesos de selección? ¿Sientes que tu voz y tus preocupaciones han sido escuchadas y atendidas?

8. ¿Sientes que los sistemas de IA en el reclutamiento pueden tener un impacto en la inclusión laboral de las personas migrantes en España? ¿De qué manera?

BLOQUE 3

1. ¿Has participado en procesos de selección de empleo en España que involucraron el uso de sistemas de inteligencia artificial o algoritmos para la toma de decisiones? Si es así, ¿en qué sectores o empresas?

2. ¿Te han explicado cómo funcionan los sistemas de IA utilizados en los procesos de selección en los que has participado? ¿Sentiste que comprendías todo el proceso de toma de decisiones de la IA y cómo afectaba el resultado final?

3. ¿Has notado alguna vez que los resultados de un proceso de selección parecían sesgados o injustos? ¿Puedes proporcionar ejemplos de situaciones en las que sentiste que podrías haber sido discriminado por un sistema de IA?

6. ¿Tienes alguna preocupación específica sobre la privacidad y seguridad de tus datos personales al participar en procesos de selección que utilizan IA? ¿Has recibido información clara sobre cómo se tratan tus datos?

7. ¿Has buscado información o recursos para comprender mejor cómo funcionan los sistemas de IA en el reclutamiento?

9. ¿Crees que las empresas deberían tener la responsabilidad de garantizar que los sistemas de IA que utilizan sean justos y equitativos para todos los candidatos, independientemente de su origen o características personales?

10. ¿Qué recomendaciones o sugerencias tendrías para mejorar la implementación de sistemas de IA en el reclutamiento y selección de personal de manera que sean más justos e inclusivos?

findhr Financiado por la Unión Europea

Más allá del algoritmo
Ampliando la comprensión de la equidad y la no discriminación en la contratación algorítmica a través del análisis de las interacciones humanas con sistemas automatizados.

1 Características que se empalman
Diagrama de Venn con tres círculos: Características demográficas, Discriminación algorítmica, y Percepciones de los usuarios.

2 Búsqueda de empleo HR
Diagrama de flujo que muestra el proceso de búsqueda de empleo HR, desde la identificación de necesidades hasta la selección final.

3 Percepciones del proceso de contratación IA
Diagrama de flujo que muestra las percepciones del proceso de contratación IA, desde la identificación de necesidades hasta la selección final.

Plataformas:
- MyWork
- Ordovador
- Clap

Mail:

Algoritmos:
- Discriminación de la raza con parámetros
- No tener de nuevo "datos" que se utilizan para discriminar

Se requiere un pago de consultoría extra cobrando más que otros:
- Renuncia y pagar solo una vez
- Regresar a otros

Redes sociales:
- LinkedIn

EUROPEA:
- Igualdad de género
- Igualdad de oportunidades
- Igualdad de acceso a la educación
- Igualdad de acceso a la salud
- Igualdad de acceso a la justicia

Desigualdad:
- Acceso por medio de la tecnología
- Acceso por medio de la tecnología
- Acceso por medio de la tecnología

Sector Social y de Economía:
- Economía social
- Acceso por medio de la tecnología
- Acceso por medio de la tecnología

SIN Discriminación:
- La selección no es automática
- Es difícil de manejar
- Que se discuta más

Inteligencia Artificial:
- Tener un Role en mejorar el proceso

IRREGULAR NO DISCRIMINACIÓN:
- Trabaja por el cliente

Irregular:
- Para trabajo pago menor
- Irregular
- Irregular
- Irregular

Regular:
- Para trabajo pago mayor
- Regular
- Regular
- Regular

Discriminación:
- Discriminación por raza
- Discriminación por género
- Discriminación por edad
- Discriminación por discapacidad

- a. ¿Creen que su conocimiento sobre tecnología es suficiente para la correcta búsqueda laboral o puede significar un bloqueo/obstáculo? ¿Sería importante acceder a un curso/capacitación para mejorar los resultados?
- b. Respecto a la tecnología, ¿Sabes si alguna vez tuviste aplicación de inteligencia artificial en los procesos de selección o conoces a alguien que tuvo esta experiencia? ¿Qué discriminaciones crees que las nuevas tecnologías, IA, podría tener hacia ti, sea por tu voz, tu cara, tus características físicas, etc?.

A4. Outreach Materials

A4.1 LinkedIn/Facebook

Hola, ¿alguna vez has realizado una búsqueda online de un puesto de trabajo y te preguntas qué tipo de sistemas están contribuyendo a la toma de decisiones sobre tu futuro profesional? 🤔

¿Te gustaría saber en qué etapas del proceso de selección se utiliza la IA? 🤖

¿Te gustaría contribuir a mejorar estos sistemas automatizados de decisión para hacerlos más inclusivos? ✨

¡Aquí tienes una oportunidad para participar y marcar la diferencia! Estamos llevando a cabo una investigación sobre la justicia algorítmica en el reclutamiento en España y tu colaboración es esencial. Este reporte se desarrolla en el marco del proyecto FINDHR liderado por la Universidad Pompeu Fabra, Wide+ y Praksis con financiamiento de la Unión Europea.

Buscamos principalmente personas de origen latinoamericano que hayan utilizado alguna plataforma en línea para su búsqueda de empleo.

Si cumples este criterio, rellena esta encuesta para descubrir más y formar parte de un cambio positivo:

📄 <https://forms.office.com/r/sYpMb1jMBx>

Si estás en Barcelona o Bilbao, también puedes unirse a uno de los grupos focales para compartir tus ideas y experiencias. (Sábado 7 de octubre de 2023 lugares por confirmar)

💡 <https://forms.gle/TGCC1RXJCC3vLX4v6>

¡Ah! Y no te olvides de donar tu CV para mejorar la justicia en el reclutamiento

👉 <https://findhr.eu/datadonation/>

¡Cada voz cuenta en nuestro esfuerzo por un futuro más inclusivo en el ámbito laboral! 📁💪

#JusticiaAlgorítmica #InclusiónLaboral #FINDHR

A4.2 Twitter

Si vives en España y eres de origen latinoamericano, queremos conocer tu experiencia en el uso de herramientas online para la búsqueda de empleo. Una investigación de @HorizonFINDHR, @EU_Commission, @upfbarcelona, @FeministWIDE, y @praksisgr

👉 Encuesta: <https://forms.office.com/r/sYpMb1jMBx>

Tweet en hilo:

¡Ah! Y no te olvides de donar tu CV para mejorar la justicia en el reclutamiento:
<https://findhr.eu/datadonation/>

Más detalles en <https://findhr.eu/>